

Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Orders - II

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Abstract

We know that we can always write **block-wise magic squares** of any order except for the orders of type p and $2p$, where p is a prime number. On the other hand we can always write **bordered magic squares** of any order. The aims of this work is to combine **bordered** and **block-wise magic squares**, for the magic squares of **prime** and **double prime** orders. We call it as **block-bordered** magic squares. The magic squares considered in this work are of orders 34, 37 and 38. In order to bring these **block-bordered** magic squares, we make use of author's previous works on **block-wise** constructions of magics squares, such as, of orders, 28, 30, 32, 35 and 36. The first part of this work [53] brings **block-bordered** magic squares of orders 11, 13, 14, 17, 19, 22, 26, 29 and 31. The third part is for the magic squares of orders 41, 43, 46 and 47.

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1 Basic Magic Squares

Below are some magic squares well known in the literature. These are of orders, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 12. In some cases, these magic squares are **pandiagonal** and or **bimagic**. These are generally used in construction of **block-wise magic squares** given in Section 3 as Appendix or Appendix 3.

1.1 Magic Square of Order 3

Example 1.1. *Let’s consider a magic square of order 3 is given by*

			15
8	1	6	15
3	5	7	15
4	9	2	15
15	15	15	15

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $3k, k > 2$.

1.2 Magic Square of Order 4

Example 1.2. *Let’s consider a pan magic square of order 4.*

		34	34	34	34
	7	12	1	14	34
34	2	13	8	11	34
34	16	3	10	5	34
34	9	6	15	4	34
	34	34	34	34	34

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $4k$, $k > 1$

1.3 Magic Square of Order 5

Example 1.3. *Let's consider a pan magic square of order 5 is given by*

		65	65	65	65	65
	1	9	12	20	23	65
65	17	25	3	6	14	65
65	8	11	19	22	5	65
65	24	2	10	13	16	65
65	15	18	21	4	7	65
	65	65	65	65	65	65

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $5k$, $k > 2$

1.4 Magic Square of Order 6

Example 1.4. *Let's consider a magic square of order 6.*

						111
1	35	34	33	2	6	111
30	8	28	9	11	25	111
24	23	15	16	20	13	111
18	14	21	22	17	19	111
7	26	10	27	29	12	111
31	5	3	4	32	36	111
111						

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $6k$, $k > 1$

1.5 Magic Square of Order 7

Example 1.5. *Let's consider a pan magic square of order 7 is given by*

		175	175	175	175	175	175	175
	1	9	17	25	33	41	49	175
175	40	48	7	8	16	24	32	175
175	23	31	39	47	6	14	15	175
175	13	21	22	30	38	46	5	175
175	45	4	12	20	28	29	37	175
175	35	36	44	3	11	19	27	175
175	18	26	34	42	43	2	10	175
	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

This magic square is used in the **block-wise** constructions of magic squares of orders $7k$, $k > 2$

1.6 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 8

Example 1.6. *Let's consider a pan magic square of order 8 is given by*

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	25	48	1	56	26	47	2	55	260
260	8	49	32	41	7	50	31	42	260
260	64	9	40	17	63	10	39	18	260
260	33	24	57	16	34	23	58	15	260
260	27	46	3	54	28	45	4	53	260
260	6	51	30	43	5	52	29	44	260
260	62	11	38	19	61	12	37	20	260
260	35	22	59	14	36	21	60	13	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of magic squares of orders $8k$, $k > 1$

Example 1.7. Let's consider a *pandiagonal bimagic square* of order 8 given by

		260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
	16	41	36	5	27	62	55	18	260
260	26	63	54	19	13	44	33	8	260
260	1	40	45	12	22	51	58	31	260
260	23	50	59	30	4	37	48	9	260
260	38	3	10	47	49	24	29	60	260
260	52	21	32	57	39	2	11	46	260
260	43	14	7	34	64	25	20	53	260
260	61	28	17	56	42	15	6	35	260
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

In this case, each 2×4 blocks entries sum is same as of magic square, i.e., 260.

This magic square is used in the block-wise constructions of bimagic squares of orders 24, 32, etc. In case of order 24 the magic square is semi-bimagic.

1.7 Magic and Bimagic Squares of Order 9

Example 1.8. Let's consider a *pandiagonal magic square* of order 9 is given by

		369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369
	8	49	66	61	24	38	36	77	10	369
369	37	63	23	12	35	76	65	7	51	369
369	78	11	34	50	64	9	22	39	62	369
369	14	28	81	67	3	53	42	56	25	369
369	52	69	2	27	41	55	80	13	30	369
369	57	26	40	29	79	15	1	54	68	369
369	20	43	60	73	18	32	48	71	4	369
369	31	75	17	6	47	70	59	19	45	369
369	72	5	46	44	58	21	16	33	74	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

Additionally, it has the property that blocks of order 3 are of equal sum as of magic square, i.e., $S_9 = 369$. Moreover, each block of order 3 is a **semi-magic square** (only in rows and columns).

Example 1.9. Let's consider a **bimagic square** of order 9 given by

									369
1	18	23	35	40	48	60	65	79	369
33	38	52	55	72	77	8	13	21	369
62	67	75	6	11	25	28	45	50	369
27	5	10	49	30	44	74	61	69	369
47	34	42	81	59	64	22	3	17	369
76	57	71	20	7	15	54	32	37	369
14	19	9	39	53	31	70	78	56	369
43	51	29	68	73	63	12	26	4	369
66	80	58	16	24	2	41	46	36	369
369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

Blocks of order 3 are of equal sum entries as of magic square, i.e., 369. The **bimagic** sum is $Sb_{9 \times 9} = 20049$.

The bimagic squares of orders 8 and 9 given in examples 1.7 and 1.9 are the classical **bimagic squares** constructed in 1891 by G. Pfeffermann [8].

1.8 Magic Squares of Order 12

In this subsection, we shall present three different ways of writing block-wise magic square of order 12. One as 4×3 , i.e., magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. Second as 3×4 , i.e., magic square formed by 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3. Third as 4 blocks of order 6 with equal magic sums. In the first two cases, the magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal**, while third case, it is just a magic square.

1.8.1 Second Approach: 12 Blocks of Order 3

Example 1.10. 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 constructed using Example 1.1 and arranging according to Example 1.2 lead us to a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 12 given by

		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
	55	45	68	96	106	83	13	27	2	126	112	137	870
870	69	56	43	82	95	108	3	14	25	136	125	114	870
870	44	67	57	107	84	94	26	1	15	113	138	124	870
870	18	28	5	121	111	134	60	46	71	91	105	80	870
870	4	17	30	135	122	109	70	59	48	81	92	103	870
870	29	6	16	110	133	123	47	72	58	104	79	93	870
870	132	118	143	19	33	8	90	100	77	49	39	62	870
870	142	131	120	9	20	31	76	89	102	63	50	37	870
870	119	144	130	32	7	21	101	78	88	38	61	51	870
870	85	99	74	54	40	65	127	117	140	24	34	11	870
870	75	86	97	64	53	42	141	128	115	10	23	36	870
870	98	73	87	41	66	52	116	139	129	35	12	22	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

We observe that it is not possible to have equal magic sums of order 3 as it is impossible to divide magic sum of order 12 by 4, i.e., $870/4=217.5$. In this case, all the 3×3 blocks are magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums giving again a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 given in example below.

Example 1.11. The magic sums of 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 appearing in Example 1.12 given above lead us to a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 given by

		870	870	870	870
	168	285	42	375	870
870	51	366	177	276	870
870	393	60	267	150	870
870	258	159	384	69	870
	870	870	870	870	870

1.8.2 First Approach: 9 Blocks of Order 4

Example 1.12. 9 blocks of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4 constructed using Example 1.2 lead us to a *pandiagonal* magic square of order 12 given by

		870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
	55	108	1	126	56	107	2	125	57	106	3	124	870
870	18	109	72	91	17	110	71	92	16	111	70	93	870
870	144	19	90	37	143	20	89	38	142	21	88	39	870
870	73	54	127	36	74	53	128	35	75	52	129	34	870
870	58	105	4	123	59	104	5	122	60	103	6	121	870
870	15	112	69	94	14	113	68	95	13	114	67	96	870
870	141	22	87	40	140	23	86	41	139	24	85	42	870
870	76	51	130	33	77	50	131	32	78	49	132	31	870
870	61	102	7	120	62	101	8	119	63	100	9	118	870
870	12	115	66	97	11	116	65	98	10	117	64	99	870
870	138	25	84	43	137	26	83	44	136	27	82	45	870
870	79	48	133	30	80	47	134	29	81	46	135	28	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{12 \times 12} = 870$. All the 4×4 blocks are **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} = 290$.

1.8.3 Third Approach: 4 Blocks of Order 6

Example 1.13. *4 blocks of magic squares of order 6 constructed using Example 1.4 lead us to a magic square of order 12 given by*

												870
1	137	136	129	8	24	2	138	135	130	7	23	870
120	32	112	33	41	97	119	31	111	34	42	98	870
96	89	57	64	80	49	95	90	58	63	79	50	870
72	56	81	88	65	73	71	55	82	87	66	74	870
25	104	40	105	113	48	26	103	39	106	114	47	870
121	17	9	16	128	144	122	18	10	15	127	143	870
3	139	134	131	6	22	4	140	133	132	5	21	870
118	30	110	35	43	99	117	29	109	36	44	100	870
94	91	59	62	78	51	93	92	60	61	77	52	870
70	54	83	86	67	75	69	53	84	85	68	76	870
27	102	38	107	115	46	28	101	37	108	116	45	870
123	19	11	14	126	142	124	20	12	13	125	141	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

In this case, the magic sum is $S_{12 \times 12} := 870$, and all the four blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums $S_{6 \times 6} := 435$.

The **magic** and **bimagic squares** written in this Section 1, are used in Section 3 for the **block-wise** constructions of different **magic** and **bimagic squares** of higher orders.

Remark 1.1. *In the next section, we worked with **bordered** magic squares. These magic square are constructed based on the online program by H. White [9, 10]. In another work, we shall write a simplified way to calculate **bordered** magic squares. Some idea on bordered magic squares can also be seen in [4, 12]. Some study on **bordered** magic square can be seen in author's work [40, 41, 42, 43, 44].*

2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares

In the previous part of this work, we wrote **block-bordered magic squares** of ordered 10, 11, 13, 17, 19, 22, 26, 29 and 31. This work deals with **block-bordered** magic squares of orders 34, 37 and 38. In this case we shall use **block-wise magic squares** of orders 28, 30, 32, 33, 35 and 36 given in Section 3 as Appendix. These results are already done before by author in different works. In parts, these results can also be calculated online by H. White [11]. In this work, most possibilities are considered.

2.1 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of order 34

Example 2.1. *Let's consider a bordered magic square of order 34 given by*

1123	1092	1094	1096	1098	1100	1102	1104	1106	1142	1144	1146	1148	1150	1152	1154	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	50	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	1124
49	1059	1030	1032	1034	1036	1038	1040	1042	1077	1079	1081	1083	1085	1087	1089	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	114	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	1060	1108
47	113	999	972	974	976	978	980	982	984	1016	1018	1020	1022	1024	1026	186	184	182	180	178	176	174	172	142	140	138	136	134	132	130	1000	1044	1110
45	111	171	943	918	920	922	924	926	928	959	961	963	965	967	969	240	238	236	234	232	230	228	199	197	195	193	191	189	187	944	986	1046	1112
43	109	169	227	891	868	870	872	874	876	878	906	908	910	912	914	290	288	286	284	282	280	278	252	250	248	246	244	242	892	930	988	1048	1114
41	107	167	225	277	843	822	824	826	828	830	857	859	861	863	865	336	334	332	330	328	326	301	299	297	295	293	291	844	880	932	990	1050	1116
39	105	165	223	275	325	799	780	782	784	786	788	812	814	816	818	378	376	374	372	370	368	346	344	342	340	338	800	832	882	934	992	1052	1118
37	103	163	221	273	323	367	759	742	744	746	748	771	773	775	777	416	414	412	410	408	387	385	383	381	379	760	790	834	884	936	994	1054	1120
35	100	161	219	271	321	365	407	723	708	710	712	714	734	736	738	450	448	446	444	442	424	422	420	418	724	750	792	836	886	938	996	1057	1122
31	99	159	216	269	319	363	405	441	691	678	680	682	701	703	705	480	478	476	474	457	455	453	451	692	716	752	794	838	888	941	998	1058	1126
29	94	155	215	267	316	361	403	439	473	663	652	654	656	672	674	506	504	502	500	486	484	482	664	684	718	754	796	841	890	942	1002	1063	1128
27	92	153	210	263	315	359	400	437	471	499	639	630	632	647	649	528	526	524	511	509	507	640	658	686	720	757	798	842	894	947	1004	1065	1130
25	90	151	208	261	310	355	399	435	468	497	523	619	612	614	626	546	544	542	532	530	620	634	660	689	722	758	802	847	896	949	1006	1067	1132
23	88	149	206	259	308	353	394	431	467	495	520	541	603	598	609	560	558	549	547	604	616	637	662	690	726	763	804	849	898	951	1008	1069	1134
21	86	147	204	257	306	351	392	429	462	491	519	539	556	591	588	570	568	562	592	601	618	638	666	695	728	765	806	851	900	953	1010	1071	1136
19	84	145	202	255	304	349	390	427	460	489	514	535	555	567	586	583	574	571	590	602	622	643	668	697	730	767	808	853	902	955	1012	1073	1138
1	82	129	200	241	302	337	388	417	458	481	512	529	550	561	572	573	584	585	596	607	628	645	676	699	740	769	820	855	916	957	1028	1075	1156
1109	1045	987	931	881	833	791	751	717	685	659	635	617	600	593	575	578	579	582	564	557	540	522	498	472	440	406	366	324	276	226	170	112	48
1111	1047	989	933	883	835	793	753	719	687	661	636	621	605	594	581	580	577	576	563	552	536	521	496	470	438	404	364	322	274	224	168	110	46
1113	1049	991	935	885	837	795	755	721	688	665	641	623	606	565	569	587	589	595	566	551	534	516	492	469	436	402	362	320	272	222	166	108	44
1115	1051	993	937	887	839	797	756	725	693	667	642	624	553	559	548	597	599	608	610	554	533	515	490	464	432	401	360	318	270	220	164	106	42
1117	1053	995	939	889	840	801	761	727	694	669	644	537	545	543	531	611	613	615	625	627	538	513	488	463	430	396	356	317	268	218	162	104	40
1119	1055	997	940	893	845	803	762	729	696	670	517	527	525	510	508	629	631	633	646	648	650	518	487	461	428	395	354	312	264	217	160	102	38
1121	1056	1001	945	895	846	805	764	731	698	493	505	503	501	485	483	651	653	655	657	671	673	675	494	459	426	393	352	311	262	212	156	101	36
1125	1061	1003	946	897	848	807	766	732	465	479	477	475	456	454	452	677	679	681	683	700	702	704	706	466	425	391	350	309	260	211	154	96	32
1127	1062	1005	948	899	850	809	768	433	449	447	445	443	423	421	419	707	709	711	713	715	733	735	737	739	434	389	348	307	258	209	152	95	30
1129	1064	1007	950	901	852	810	397	415	413	411	409	386	384	382	380	741	743	745	747	749	770	772	774	776	778	398	347	305	256	207	150	93	28
1131	1066	1009	952	903	854	357	377	375	373	371	369	345	343	341	339	779	781	783	785	787	789	811	813	815	817	819	358	303	254	205	148	91	26
1133	1068	1011	954	904	313	335	333	331	329	327	300	298	296	294	292	821	823	825	827	829	831	856	858	860	862	864	866	314	253	203	146	89	24
1135	1070	1013	956	265	289	287	285	283	281	279	251	249	247	245	243	867	869	871	873	875	877	879	905	907	909	911	913	915	266	201	144	87	22
1137	1072	1014	213	239	237	235	233	231	229	198	196	194	192	190	188	917	919	921	923	925	927	929	958	960	962	964	966	968	970	214	143	85	20
1139	1074	157	185	183	181	179	177	175	173	141	139	137	135	133	131	971	973	975	977	979	981	983	985	1015	1017	1019	1021	1023	1025	1027	158	83	18
1140	97	127	125	123	121	119	117	115	80	78	76	74	72	70	68	1029	1031	1033	1035	1037	1039	1041	1043	1076	1078	1080	1082	1084	1086	1088	1090	98	17
33	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1091	1093	1095	1097	1099	1101	1103	1105	1107	1141	1143	1145	1147	1149	1151	1153	1155	34

The above magic square is formed by the following distributions and magic sums:

$$D_{4 \times 4} := \{571, 572, \dots, 0, 585, 586\}$$

$$S_{4 \times 4} := 2314$$

$$D_{6 \times 6} := \{561, 562, \dots, 569, 570, D_{4 \times 4}, 587, 588, \dots, 595, 596\}$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 3471$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{547, 548, \dots, 559, 560, D_{6 \times 6}, 597, 598, \dots, 609, 610\} & S_{8 \times 8} &:= 4628 \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{529, 530, \dots, 545, 546, D_{8 \times 8}, 611, 612, \dots, 607, 628\} & S_{10 \times 10} &:= 5785 \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{507, 508, \dots, 527, 528, D_{10 \times 10}, 629, 630, \dots, 649, 650\} & S_{12 \times 12} &:= 6942 \\
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{481, 482, \dots, 505, 506, D_{12 \times 12}, 651, 665, \dots, 675, 676\} & S_{14 \times 14} &:= 8099 \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{451, 452, \dots, 479, 480, D_{14 \times 14}, 677, 678, \dots, 705, 706\} & S_{16 \times 16} &:= 9256 \\
 D_{18 \times 18} &:= \{417, 418, \dots, 449, 450, D_{16 \times 16}, 707, 708, \dots, 739, 740\} & S_{18 \times 18} &:= 10413 \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{379, 380, \dots, 415, 416, D_{18 \times 18}, 741, 742, \dots, 777, 778\} & S_{20 \times 20} &:= 11570 \\
 D_{22 \times 22} &:= \{337, 338, \dots, 377, 378, D_{20 \times 20}, 779, 780, \dots, 819, 820\} & S_{22 \times 22} &:= 12727 \\
 D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{291, 292, \dots, 335, 336, D_{22 \times 22}, 821, 822, \dots, 865, 866\} & S_{24 \times 24} &:= 13884 \\
 D_{26 \times 26} &:= \{241, 242, \dots, 289, 290, D_{24 \times 24}, 867, 868, \dots, 911, 916\} & S_{26 \times 26} &:= 15041 \\
 D_{28 \times 28} &:= \{187, 188, \dots, 239, 240, D_{26 \times 26}, 917, 914, \dots, 969, 970\} & S_{28 \times 28} &:= 16198 \\
 D_{30 \times 30} &:= \{129, 130, \dots, 185, 186, D_{28 \times 28}, 971, 972, \dots, 1005, 1028\} & S_{30 \times 30} &:= 17355 \\
 D_{32 \times 32} &:= \{67, 68, \dots, 127, 128, D_{30 \times 30}, 1029, 1030, \dots, 1063, 1090\} & S_{32 \times 32} &:= 18512 \\
 D_{34 \times 34} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 65, 66, D_{32 \times 32}, 1091, 1092, \dots, 1155, 1156\} & S_{34 \times 34} &:= 19669.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are nine different ways of writing **block-bordered magic squares** of order 34. These different ways are based on the magic squares of orders 32, 30 and 28 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.11, 3.12, 3.5, 3.7, 3.9, 3.10, 3.1, 3.2 and 3.4.

2.1.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1156 by 67 to 1090 in Example 3.11 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{32 \times 32}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 given by

1123	1092	1094	1096	1098	1100	1102	1104	1106	1142	1144	1146	1148	1150	1152	1154	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	50	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	1124
49	451	834	67	962	452	833	68	961	453	832	69	960	454	831	70	959	455	830	71	958	456	829	72	957	457	828	73	956	458	827	74	955	1108
47	194	835	578	707	193	836	577	708	192	837	576	709	191	838	575	710	190	839	574	711	189	840	573	712	188	841	572	713	187	842	571	714	1110
45	1090	195	706	323	1089	196	705	324	1088	197	704	325	1087	198	703	326	1086	199	702	327	1085	200	701	328	1084	201	700	329	1083	202	699	330	1112
43	579	450	963	322	580	449	964	321	581	448	965	320	582	447	966	319	583	446	967	318	584	445	968	317	585	444	969	316	586	443	970	315	1114
41	459	826	75	954	460	825	76	953	461	824	77	952	462	823	78	951	463	822	79	950	464	821	80	949	465	820	81	948	466	819	82	947	1116
39	186	843	570	715	185	844	569	716	184	845	568	717	183	846	567	718	182	847	566	719	181	848	565	720	180	849	564	721	179	850	563	722	1118
37	1082	203	698	331	1081	204	697	332	1080	205	696	333	1079	206	695	334	1078	207	694	335	1077	208	693	336	1076	209	692	337	1075	210	691	338	1120
35	587	442	971	314	588	441	972	313	589	440	973	312	590	439	974	311	591	438	975	310	592	437	976	309	593	436	977	308	594	435	978	307	1122
31	467	818	83	946	468	817	84	945	469	816	85	944	470	815	86	943	471	814	87	942	472	813	88	941	473	812	89	940	474	811	90	939	1126
29	178	851	562	723	177	852	561	724	176	853	560	725	175	854	559	726	174	855	558	727	173	856	557	728	172	857	556	729	171	858	555	730	1128
27	1074	211	690	339	1073	212	689	340	1072	213	688	341	1071	214	687	342	1070	215	686	343	1069	216	685	344	1068	217	684	345	1067	218	683	346	1130
25	595	434	979	306	596	433	980	305	597	432	981	304	598	431	982	303	599	430	983	302	600	429	984	301	601	428	985	300	602	427	986	299	1132
23	475	810	91	938	476	809	92	937	477	808	93	936	478	807	94	935	479	806	95	934	480	805	96	933	481	804	97	932	482	803	98	931	1134
21	170	859	554	731	169	860	553	732	168	861	552	733	167	862	551	734	166	863	550	735	165	864	549	736	164	865	548	737	163	866	547	738	1136
19	1066	219	682	347	1065	220	681	348	1064	221	680	349	1063	222	679	350	1062	223	678	351	1061	224	677	352	1060	225	676	353	1059	226	675	354	1138
1	603	426	987	298	604	425	988	297	605	424	989	296	606	423	990	295	607	422	991	294	608	421	992	293	609	420	993	292	610	419	994	291	1156
1109	483	802	99	930	484	801	100	929	485	800	101	928	486	799	102	927	487	798	103	926	488	797	104	925	489	796	105	924	490	795	106	923	48
1111	162	867	546	739	161	868	545	740	160	869	544	741	159	870	543	742	158	871	542	743	157	872	541	744	156	873	540	745	155	874	539	746	46
1113	1058	227	674	355	1057	228	673	356	1056	229	672	357	1055	230	671	358	1054	231	670	359	1053	232	669	360	1052	233	668	361	1051	234	667	362	44
1115	611	418	995	290	612	417	996	289	613	416	997	288	614	415	998	287	615	414	999	286	616	413	1000	285	617	412	1001	284	618	411	1002	283	42
1117	491	794	107	922	492	793	108	921	493	792	109	920	494	791	110	919	495	790	111	918	496	789	112	917	497	788	113	916	498	787	114	915	40
1119	154	875	538	747	153	876	537	748	152	877	536	749	151	878	535	750	150	879	534	751	149	880	533	752	148	881	532	753	147	882	531	754	38
1121	1050	235	666	363	1049	236	665	364	1048	237	664	365	1047	238	663	366	1046	239	662	367	1045	240	661	368	1044	241	660	369	1043	242	659	370	36
1125	619	410	1003	282	620	409	1004	281	621	408	1005	280	622	407	1006	279	623	406	1007	278	624	405	1008	277	625	404	1009	276	626	403	1010	275	32
1127	499	786	115	914	500	785	116	913	501	784	117	912	502	783	118	911	503	782	119	910	504	781	120	909	505	780	121	908	506	779	122	907	30
1129	146	883	530	755	145	884	529	756	144	885	528	757	143	886	527	758	142	887	526	759	141	888	525	760	140	889	524	761	139	890	523	762	28
1131	1042	243	658	371	1041	244	657	372	1040	245	656	373	1039	246	655	374	1038	247	654	375	1037	248	653	376	1036	249	652	377	1035	250	651	378	26
1133	627	402	1011	274	628	401	1012	273	629	400	1013	272	630	399	1014	271	631	398	1015	270	632	397	1016	269	633	396	1017	268	634	395	1018	267	24
1135	507	778	123	906	508	777	124	905	509	776	125	904	510	775	126	903	511	774	127	902	512	773	128	901	513	772	129	900	514	771	130	899	22
1137	138	891	522	763	137	892	521	764	136	893	520	765	135	894	519	766	134	895	518	767	133	896	517	768	132	897	516	769	131	898	515	770	20
1139	1034	251	650	379	1033	252	649	380	1032	253	648	381	1031	254	647	382	1030	255	646	383	1029	256	645	384	1028	257	644	385	1027	258	643	386	18
1140	635	394	1019	266	636	393	1020	265	637	392	1021	264	638	391	1022	263	639	390	1023	262	640	389	1024	261	641	388	1025	260	642	387	1026	259	17
33	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1091	1093	1095	1097	1099	1101	1103	1105	1107	1141	1143	1145	1147	1149	1151	1153	1155	34

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34, where the magic square of order 32 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 19669, \quad S_{32 \times 32} := 18512 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{4 \times 4} := 2314.$$

Blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

2.1.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1156 by 67 to 1090 in Example 3.12 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{32 \times 32}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 given by

1123	1092	1094	1096	1098	1100	1102	1104	1106	1142	1144	1146	1148	1150	1152	1154	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	50	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	1124
49	288	773	624	117	525	1048	893	360	255	742	655	150	494	1015	926	391	322	803	594	83	555	1082	859	330	225	708	689	180	460	985	956	425	1108
47	520	1053	888	365	277	784	613	128	487	1022	919	398	246	751	646	159	554	1083	858	331	307	818	579	98	457	988	953	428	212	721	676	193	1110
45	101	640	789	272	376	877	1032	541	134	671	758	239	407	910	999	510	67	610	819	306	346	843	1066	571	164	705	724	209	441	940	969	476	1112
43	381	872	1037	536	112	629	800	261	414	903	1006	503	143	662	767	230	347	842	1067	570	82	595	834	291	444	937	972	473	177	692	737	196	1114
41	632	109	264	797	869	384	533	1040	663	142	231	766	902	415	502	1007	602	75	298	827	835	354	563	1074	697	172	201	732	932	449	468	977	1116
39	880	373	544	1029	637	104	269	792	911	406	511	998	670	135	238	759	850	339	578	1059	603	74	299	826	945	436	481	964	700	169	204	729	1118
37	781	280	125	616	1056	517	368	885	750	247	158	647	1023	486	399	918	811	314	91	586	1090	547	338	851	716	217	188	681	993	452	433	948	1120
35	1045	528	357	896	776	285	120	621	1014	495	390	927	743	254	151	654	1075	562	323	866	810	315	90	587	980	465	420	961	713	220	185	684	1122
31	321	804	593	84	556	1081	860	329	226	707	690	179	459	986	955	426	287	774	623	118	526	1047	894	359	256	741	656	149	493	1016	925	392	1126
29	553	1084	857	332	308	817	580	97	458	987	954	427	211	722	675	194	519	1054	887	366	278	783	614	127	488	1021	920	397	245	752	645	160	1128
27	68	609	820	305	345	844	1065	572	163	706	723	210	442	939	970	475	102	639	790	271	375	878	1031	542	133	672	757	240	408	909	1000	509	1130
25	348	841	1068	569	81	596	833	292	443	938	971	474	178	691	738	195	382	871	1038	535	111	630	799	262	413	904	1005	504	144	661	768	229	1132
23	601	76	297	828	836	353	564	1073	698	171	202	731	931	450	467	978	631	110	263	798	870	383	534	1039	664	141	232	765	901	416	501	1008	1134
21	849	340	577	1060	604	73	300	825	946	435	482	963	699	170	203	730	879	374	543	1030	638	103	270	791	912	405	512	997	669	136	237	760	1136
19	812	313	92	585	1089	548	337	852	715	218	187	682	994	451	434	947	782	279	126	615	1055	518	367	886	749	248	157	648	1024	485	400	917	1138
1	1076	561	324	865	809	316	89	588	979	466	419	962	714	219	186	683	1046	527	358	895	775	286	119	622	1013	496	389	928	744	253	152	653	1156
1109	223	710	687	182	462	983	958	423	320	805	592	85	557	1080	861	328	257	740	657	148	492	1017	924	393	290	771	626	115	523	1050	891	362	48
1111	455	990	951	430	214	719	678	191	552	1085	856	333	309	816	581	96	489	1020	921	396	244	753	644	161	522	1051	890	363	275	786	611	130	46
1113	166	703	726	207	439	942	967	478	69	608	821	304	344	845	1064	573	132	673	756	241	409	908	1001	508	99	642	787	274	378	875	1034	539	44
1115	446	935	974	471	175	694	735	198	349	840	1069	568	80	597	832	293	412	905	1004	505	145	660	769	228	379	874	1035	538	114	627	802	259	42
1117	695	174	199	734	934	447	470	975	600	77	296	829	837	352	565	1072	665	140	233	764	900	417	500	1009	634	107	266	795	867	386	531	1042	40
1119	943	438	479	966	702	167	206	727	848	341	576	1061	605	72	301	824	913	404	513	996	668	137	236	761	882	371	546	1027	635	106	267	794	38
1121	718	215	190	679	991	454	431	950	813	312	93	584	1088	549	336	853	748	249	156	649	1025	484	401	916	779	282	123	618	1058	515	370	883	36
1125	982	463	422	959	711	222	183	686	1077	560	325	864	808	317	88	589	1012	497	388	929	745	252	153	652	1043	530	355	898	778	283	122	619	32
1127	258	739	658	147	491	1018	923	394	289	772	625	116	524	1049	892	361	224	709	688	181	461	984	957	424	319	806	591	86	558	1079	862	327	30
1129	490	1019	922	395	243	754	643	162	521	1052	889	364	276	785	612	129	456	989	952	429	213	720	677	192	551	1086	855	334	310	815	582	95	28
1131	131	674	755	242	410	907	1002	507	100	641	788	273	377	876	1033	540	165	704	725	208	440	941	968	477	70	607	822	303	343	846	1063	574	26
1133	411	906	1003	506	146	659	770	227	380	873	1036	537	113	628	801	260	445	936	973	472	176	693	736	197	350	839	1070	567	79	598	831	294	24
1135	666	139	234	763	899	418	499	1010	633	108	265	796	868	385	532	1041	696	173	200	733	933	448	469	976	599	78	295	830	838	351	566	1071	22
1137	914	403	514	995	667	138	235	762	881	372	545	1028	636	105	268	793	944	437	480	965	701	168	205	728	847	342	575	1062	606	71	302	823	20
1139	747	250	155	650	1026	483	402	915	780	281	124	617	1057	516	369	884	717	216	189	680	992	453	432	949	814	311	94	583	1087	550	335	854	18
1140	1011	498	387	930	746	251	154	651	1044	529	356	897	777	284	121	620	981	464	421	960	712	221	184	685	1078	559	326	863	807	318	87	590	17
33	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1091	1093	1095	1097	1099	1101	1103	1105	1107	1141	1143	1145	1147	1149	1151	1153	1155	34

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34, where magic squares of order 32 is **pandiagonal** and **bimagic** with following sums:

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 19669, \quad S_{32 \times 32} := 18512 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{8 \times 8} := 4628.$$

Blocks of order 8 are **pandigonal magic squares** with equal magic sums. Moreover each block of order 8 is either **bimagic** or **semi-bimagic** resulting in a **pandiagonal bimagic square** of order 32 with **bimagic sum**, $Sb_{32 \times 32} := 13505392..$

2.1.3 Third Way

Replace the entries 1 to 900 by 129 to 1028 in Example 3.5 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{30 \times 30}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 given by

1123	1092	1094	1096	1098	1100	1102	1104	1106	1142	1144	1146	1148	1150	1152	1154	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	50	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	1124
49	1059	1030	1032	1034	1036	1038	1040	1042	1077	1079	1081	1083	1085	1087	1089	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	114	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	1060	1108
47	113	159	191	130	993	965	1024	536	564	505	704	732	673	272	240	301	800	768	829	621	593	652	897	929	868	368	396	337	435	407	466	1044	1110
45	111	131	160	189	1025	994	963	504	535	566	672	703	734	300	271	242	828	799	770	653	622	591	869	898	927	336	367	398	467	436	405	1046	1112
43	109	190	129	161	964	1023	995	565	506	534	733	674	702	241	302	270	769	830	798	592	651	623	928	867	899	397	338	366	406	465	437	1048	1114
41	107	806	774	835	254	222	283	992	960	1021	525	557	496	638	606	667	453	425	484	879	911	850	170	198	139	711	743	682	357	389	328	1050	1116
39	105	834	805	776	282	253	224	1020	991	962	497	526	555	666	637	608	485	454	423	851	880	909	138	169	200	683	712	741	329	358	387	1052	1118
37	103	775	836	804	223	284	252	961	1022	990	556	495	527	607	668	636	424	483	455	910	849	881	199	140	168	742	681	713	388	327	359	1054	1120
35	100	524	552	493	722	750	691	345	377	316	908	936	877	446	414	475	267	239	298	813	785	844	609	581	640	980	948	1009	171	203	142	1057	1122
31	99	492	523	554	690	721	752	317	346	375	876	907	938	474	445	416	299	268	237	845	814	783	641	610	579	1008	979	950	143	172	201	1058	1126
29	94	553	494	522	751	692	720	376	315	347	937	878	906	415	476	444	238	297	269	784	843	815	580	639	611	949	1010	978	202	141	173	1063	1128
27	92	728	756	697	177	209	148	801	773	832	440	408	469	339	371	310	885	917	856	542	570	511	974	942	1003	266	234	295	633	605	664	1065	1130
25	90	696	727	758	149	178	207	833	802	771	468	439	410	311	340	369	857	886	915	510	541	572	1002	973	944	294	265	236	665	634	603	1067	1132
23	88	757	698	726	208	147	179	772	831	803	409	470	438	370	309	341	916	855	887	571	512	540	943	1004	972	235	296	264	604	663	635	1069	1134
21	86	620	588	649	429	401	460	723	755	694	807	779	838	531	563	502	344	372	313	986	954	1015	278	246	307	165	197	136	902	930	871	1071	1136
19	84	648	619	590	461	430	399	695	724	753	839	808	777	503	532	561	312	343	374	1014	985	956	306	277	248	137	166	195	870	901	932	1073	1138
1	82	589	650	618	400	459	431	754	693	725	778	837	809	562	501	533	373	314	342	955	1016	984	247	308	276	196	135	167	931	872	900	1075	1156
1109	1045	891	923	862	530	558	499	249	221	280	363	395	334	987	959	1018	626	594	655	188	216	157	705	737	676	452	420	481	794	762	823	112	48
1111	1047	863	892	921	498	529	560	281	250	219	335	364	393	1019	988	957	654	625	596	156	187	218	677	706	735	480	451	422	822	793	764	110	46
1113	1049	922	861	893	559	500	528	220	279	251	394	333	365	958	1017	989	595	656	624	217	158	186	736	675	707	421	482	450	763	824	792	108	44
1115	1051	362	390	331	615	587	646	458	426	487	176	204	145	884	912	853	981	953	1012	717	749	688	543	575	514	789	761	820	260	228	289	106	42
1117	1053	330	361	392	647	616	585	486	457	428	144	175	206	852	883	914	1013	982	951	689	718	747	515	544	573	821	790	759	288	259	230	104	40
1119	1055	391	332	360	586	645	617	427	488	456	205	146	174	913	854	882	952	1011	983	748	687	719	574	513	545	760	819	791	229	290	258	102	38
1121	1056	447	419	478	351	383	322	890	918	859	969	941	1000	183	215	154	548	576	517	255	227	286	812	780	841	614	582	643	716	744	685	101	36
1125	1061	479	448	417	323	352	381	858	889	920	1001	970	939	155	184	213	516	547	578	287	256	225	840	811	782	642	613	584	684	715	746	96	32
1127	1062	418	477	449	382	321	353	919	860	888	940	999	971	214	153	185	577	518	546	226	285	257	781	842	810	583	644	612	745	686	714	95	30
1129	1064	975	947	1006	818	786	847	627	599	658	261	233	292	710	738	679	182	210	151	434	402	463	356	384	325	903	935	874	519	551	490	93	28
1131	1066	1007	976	945	846	817	788	659	628	597	293	262	231	678	709	740	150	181	212	462	433	404	324	355	386	875	904	933	491	520	549	91	26
1133	1068	946	1005	977	787	848	816	598	657	629	232	291	263	739	680	708	211	152	180	403	464	432	385	326	354	934	873	905	550	489	521	89	24
1135	1070	273	245	304	896	924	865	164	192	133	632	600	661	795	767	826	699	731	670	350	378	319	441	413	472	537	569	508	998	966	1027	87	22
1137	1072	305	274	243	864	895	926	132	163	194	660	631	602	827	796	765	671	700	729	318	349	380	473	442	411	509	538	567	1026	997	968	85	20
1139	1074	244	303	275	925	866	894	193	134	162	601	662	630	766	825	797	730	669	701	379	320	348	412	471	443	568	507	539	967	1028	996	83	18
1140	97	127	125	123	121	119	117	115	80	78	76	74	72	70	68	1029	1031	1033	1035	1037	1039	1041	1043	1076	1078	1080	1082	1084	1086	1088	1090	98	17
33	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1091	1093	1095	1097	1099	1101	1103	1105	1107	1141	1143	1145	1147	1149	1151	1153	1155	34

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 with following sums:

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 19669, \quad S_{32 \times 32} := 18512 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{30 \times 30} := 17355.$$

Blocks of order 3 are **magic squares** with **different magic sums**.

2.1.4 Forth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 900 by 129 to 1028 in Example 3.7 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{30 \times 30}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 given by

1123	1092	1094	1096	1098	1100	1102	1104	1106	1142	1144	1146	1148	1150	1152	1154	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	50	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	1124
49	1059	1030	1032	1034	1036	1038	1040	1042	1077	1079	1081	1083	1085	1087	1089	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	114	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	1060	1108
47	113	129	417	525	813	921	151	439	547	835	943	156	444	552	840	948	162	450	558	846	954	145	433	541	829	937	136	424	532	820	928	1044	1110
45	111	705	993	201	309	597	727	1015	223	331	619	732	1020	228	336	624	738	1026	234	342	630	721	1009	217	325	613	712	1000	208	316	604	1046	1112
43	109	381	489	777	885	273	403	511	799	907	295	408	516	804	912	300	414	522	810	918	306	397	505	793	901	289	388	496	784	892	280	1048	1114
41	107	957	165	453	561	669	979	187	475	583	691	984	192	480	588	696	990	198	486	594	702	973	181	469	577	685	964	172	460	568	676	1050	1116
39	105	633	741	849	237	345	655	763	871	259	367	660	768	876	264	372	666	774	882	270	378	649	757	865	253	361	640	748	856	244	352	1052	1118
37	103	157	445	553	841	949	135	423	531	819	927	163	451	559	847	955	142	430	538	826	934	149	437	545	833	941	133	421	529	817	925	1054	1120
35	100	733	1021	229	337	625	711	999	207	315	603	739	1027	235	343	631	718	1006	214	322	610	725	1013	221	329	617	709	997	205	313	601	1057	1122
31	99	409	517	805	913	301	387	495	783	891	279	415	523	811	919	307	394	502	790	898	286	401	509	797	905	293	385	493	781	889	277	1058	1126
29	94	985	193	481	589	697	963	171	459	567	675	991	199	487	595	703	970	178	466	574	682	977	185	473	581	689	961	169	457	565	673	1063	1128
27	92	661	769	877	265	373	639	747	855	243	351	667	775	883	271	379	646	754	862	250	358	653	761	869	257	365	637	745	853	241	349	1065	1130
25	90	140	428	536	824	932	134	422	530	818	926	141	429	537	825	933	155	443	551	839	947	159	447	555	843	951	150	438	546	834	942	1067	1132
23	88	716	1004	212	320	608	710	998	206	314	602	717	1005	213	321	609	731	1019	227	335	623	735	1023	231	339	627	726	1014	222	330	618	1069	1134
21	86	392	500	788	896	284	386	494	782	890	278	393	501	789	897	285	407	515	803	911	299	411	519	807	915	303	402	510	798	906	294	1071	1136
19	84	968	176	464	572	680	962	170	458	566	674	969	177	465	573	681	983	191	479	587	695	987	195	483	591	699	978	186	474	582	690	1073	1138
1	82	644	752	860	248	356	638	746	854	242	350	645	753	861	249	357	659	767	875	263	371	663	771	879	267	375	654	762	870	258	366	1075	1156
1109	1045	160	448	556	844	952	144	432	540	828	936	132	420	528	816	924	152	440	548	836	944	138	426	534	822	930	153	441	549	837	945	112	48
1111	1047	736	1024	232	340	628	720	1008	216	324	612	708	996	204	312	600	728	1016	224	332	620	714	1002	210	318	606	729	1017	225	333	621	110	46
1113	1049	412	520	808	916	304	396	504	792	900	288	384	492	780	888	276	404	512	800	908	296	390	498	786	894	282	405	513	801	909	297	108	44
1115	1051	988	196	484	592	700	972	180	468	576	684	960	168	456	564	672	980	188	476	584	692	966	174	462	570	678	981	189	477	585	693	106	42
1117	1053	664	772	880	268	376	648	756	864	252	360	636	744	852	240	348	656	764	872	260	368	642	750	858	246	354	657	765	873	261	369	104	40
1119	1055	147	435	543	831	939	161	449	557	845	953	139	427	535	823	931	131	419	527	815	923	158	446	554	842	950	143	431	539	827	935	102	38
1121	1056	723	1011	219	327	615	737	1025	233	341	629	715	1003	211	319	607	707	995	203	311	599	734	1022	230	338	626	719	1007	215	323	611	101	36
1125	1061	399	507	795	903	291	413	521	809	917	305	391	499	787	895	283	383	491	779	887	275	410	518	806	914	302	395	503	791	899	287	96	32
1127	1062	975	183	471	579	687	989	197	485	593	701	967	175	463	571	679	959	167	455	563	671	986	194	482	590	698	971	179	467	575	683	95	30
1129	1064	651	759	867	255	363	665	773	881	269	377	643	751	859	247	355	635	743	851	239	347	662	770	878	266	374	647	755	863	251	359	93	28
1131	1066	146	434	542	830	938	154	442	550	838	946	148	436	544	832	940	137	425	533	821	929	130	418	526	814	922	164	452	560	848	956	91	26
1133	1068	722	1010	218	326	614	730	1018	226	334	622	724	1012	220	328	616	713	1001	209	317	605	706	994	202	310	598	740	1028	236	344	632	89	24
1135	1070	398	506	794	902	290	406	514	802	910	298	400	508	796	904	292	389	497	785	893	281	382	490	778	886	274	416	524	812	920	308	87	22
1137	1072	974	182	470	578	686	982	190	478	586	694	976	184	472	580	688	965	173	461	569	677	958	166	454	562	670	992	200	488	596	704	85	20
1139	1074	650	758	866	254	362	658	766	874	262	370	652	760	868	256	364	641	749	857	245	353	634	742	850	238	346	668	776	884	272	380	83	18
1140	97	127	125	123	121	119	117	115	80	78	76	74	72	70	68	1029	1031	1033	1035	1037	1039	1041	1043	1076	1078	1080	1082	1084	1086	1088	1090	98	17
33	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1091	1093	1095	1097	1099	1101	1103	1105	1107	1141	1143	1145	1147	1149	1151	1153	1155	34

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 with following sums:

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 19669, \quad S_{32 \times 32} := 18512 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{30 \times 30} := 17355.$$

Blocks of order 5×5 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **different magic sums**.

2.1.5 Fifth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 900 by 129 to 1028 in Example 3.9 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{30 \times 30}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 given by

1123	1092	1094	1096	1098	1100	1102	1104	1106	1142	1144	1146	1148	1150	1152	1154	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	50	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	1124
49	1059	1030	1032	1034	1036	1038	1040	1042	1077	1079	1081	1083	1085	1087	1089	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	114	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	1060	1108
47	113	129	979	978	929	178	278	130	980	977	930	177	277	131	981	976	931	176	276	132	982	975	932	175	275	133	983	974	933	174	274	1044	1110
45	111	878	328	828	329	379	729	877	327	827	330	380	730	876	326	826	331	381	731	875	325	825	332	382	732	874	324	824	333	383	733	1046	1112
43	109	728	679	479	528	628	429	727	680	480	527	627	430	726	681	481	526	626	431	725	682	482	525	625	432	724	683	483	524	624	433	1048	1114
41	107	578	478	629	678	529	579	577	477	630	677	530	580	576	476	631	676	531	581	575	475	632	675	532	582	574	474	633	674	533	583	1050	1116
39	105	279	778	378	779	829	428	280	777	377	780	830	427	281	776	376	781	831	426	282	775	375	782	832	425	283	774	374	783	833	424	1052	1118
37	103	879	229	179	228	928	1028	880	230	180	227	927	1027	881	231	181	226	926	1026	882	232	182	225	925	1025	883	233	183	224	924	1024	1054	1120
35	100	134	984	973	934	173	273	135	985	972	935	172	272	136	986	971	936	171	271	137	987	970	937	170	270	138	988	969	938	169	269	1057	1122
31	99	873	323	823	334	384	734	872	322	822	335	385	735	871	321	821	336	386	736	870	320	820	337	387	737	869	319	819	338	388	738	1058	1126
29	94	723	684	484	523	623	434	722	685	485	522	622	435	721	686	486	521	621	436	720	687	487	520	620	437	719	688	488	519	619	438	1063	1128
27	92	573	473	634	673	534	584	572	472	635	672	535	585	571	471	636	671	536	586	570	470	637	670	537	587	569	469	638	669	538	588	1065	1130
25	90	284	773	373	784	834	423	285	772	372	785	835	422	286	771	371	786	836	421	287	770	370	787	837	420	288	769	369	788	838	419	1067	1132
23	88	884	234	184	223	923	1023	885	235	185	222	922	1022	886	236	186	221	921	1021	887	237	187	220	920	1020	888	238	188	219	919	1019	1069	1134
21	86	139	989	968	939	168	268	140	990	967	940	167	267	141	991	966	941	166	266	142	992	965	942	165	265	143	993	964	943	164	264	1071	1136
19	84	868	318	818	339	389	739	867	317	817	340	390	740	866	316	816	341	391	741	865	315	815	342	392	742	864	314	814	343	393	743	1073	1138
1	82	718	689	489	518	618	439	717	690	490	517	617	440	716	691	491	516	616	441	715	692	492	515	615	442	714	693	493	514	614	443	1075	1156
1109	1045	568	468	639	668	539	589	567	467	640	667	540	590	566	466	641	666	541	591	565	465	642	665	542	592	564	464	643	664	543	593	112	48
1111	1047	289	768	368	789	839	418	290	767	367	790	840	417	291	766	366	791	841	416	292	765	365	792	842	415	293	764	364	793	843	414	110	46
1113	1049	889	239	189	218	918	1018	890	240	190	217	917	1017	891	241	191	216	916	1016	892	242	192	215	915	1015	893	243	193	214	914	1014	108	44
1115	1051	144	994	963	944	163	263	145	995	962	945	162	262	146	996	961	946	161	261	147	997	960	947	160	260	148	998	959	948	159	259	106	42
1117	1053	863	313	813	344	394	744	862	312	812	345	395	745	861	311	811	346	396	746	860	310	810	347	397	747	859	309	809	348	398	748	104	40
1119	1055	713	694	494	513	613	444	712	695	495	512	612	445	711	696	496	511	611	446	710	697	497	510	610	447	709	698	498	509	609	448	102	38
1121	1056	563	463	644	663	544	594	562	462	645	662	545	595	561	461	646	661	546	596	560	460	647	660	547	597	559	459	648	659	548	598	101	36
1125	1061	294	763	363	794	844	413	295	762	362	795	845	412	296	761	361	796	846	411	297	760	360	797	847	410	298	759	359	798	848	409	96	32
1127	1062	894	244	194	213	913	1013	895	245	195	212	912	1012	896	246	196	211	911	1011	897	247	197	210	910	1010	898	248	198	209	909	1009	95	30
1129	1064	149	999	958	949	158	258	150	1000	957	950	157	257	151	1001	956	951	156	256	152	1002	955	952	155	255	153	1003	954	953	154	254	93	28
1131	1066	858	308	808	349	399	749	857	307	807	350	400	750	856	306	806	351	401	751	855	305	805	352	402	752	854	304	804	353	403	753	91	26
1133	1068	708	699	499	508	608	449	707	700	500	507	607	450	706	701	501	506	606	451	705	702	502	505	605	452	704	703	503	504	604	453	89	24
1135	1070	558	458	649	658	549	599	557	457	650	657	550	600	556	456	651	656	551	601	555	455	652	655	552	602	554	454	653	654	553	603	87	22
1137	1072	299	758	358	799	849	408	300	757	357	800	850	407	301	756	356	801	851	406	302	755	355	802	852	405	303	754	354	803	853	404	85	20
1139	1074	899	249	199	208	908	1008	900	250	200	207	907	1007	901	251	201	206	906	1006	902	252	202	205	905	1005	903	253	203	204	904	1004	83	18
1140	97	127	125	123	121	119	117	115	80	78	76	74	72	70	68	1029	1031	1033	1035	1037	1039	1041	1043	1076	1078	1080	1082	1084	1086	1088	1090	98	17
33	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1091	1093	1095	1097	1099	1101	1103	1105	1107	1141	1143	1145	1147	1149	1151	1153	1155	34

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 with following sums:

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 19669, \quad S_{32 \times 32} := 18512, \quad S_{30 \times 30} := 17355 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{6 \times 6} := 3471.$$

Blocks of order 6 are **magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

2.1.6 Sixth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 900 by 129 to 1028 in Example 3.10 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{30 \times 30}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 given by

1123	1092	1094	1096	1098	1100	1102	1104	1106	1142	1144	1146	1148	1150	1152	1154	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	50	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	1124
49	1059	1030	1032	1034	1036	1038	1040	1042	1077	1079	1081	1083	1085	1087	1089	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	114	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	1060	1108
47	113	129	848	705	993	471	326	560	902	597	254	130	847	706	994	472	325	559	901	598	253	131	846	707	995	473	324	558	900	599	252	1044	1110
45	111	1010	236	201	722	938	794	615	417	489	363	1009	235	202	721	937	793	616	418	490	364	1008	234	203	720	936	792	617	419	491	365	1046	1112
43	109	543	849	327	831	272	435	974	668	686	200	544	850	328	832	271	436	973	667	685	199	545	851	329	833	270	437	972	666	684	198	1048	1114
41	107	758	633	920	434	146	939	381	255	812	507	757	634	919	433	145	940	382	256	811	508	756	635	918	432	144	941	383	257	810	509	1050	1116
39	105	884	1011	596	219	525	740	777	183	398	452	883	1012	595	220	526	739	778	184	397	451	882	1013	594	221	527	738	779	185	396	450	1052	1118
37	103	237	470	524	218	813	632	866	309	975	741	238	469	523	217	814	631	865	310	976	742	239	468	522	216	815	630	864	311	977	743	1054	1120
35	100	795	542	488	867	380	291	723	956	164	579	796	541	487	868	379	292	724	955	163	580	797	540	486	869	378	293	725	954	162	581	1057	1122
31	99	651	344	992	506	669	147	308	830	453	885	652	343	991	505	670	148	307	829	454	886	653	342	990	504	671	149	306	828	455	887	1058	1126
29	94	362	165	273	650	957	578	399	704	921	776	361	166	274	649	958	577	400	703	922	775	360	167	275	648	959	576	401	702	923	774	1063	1128
27	92	416	687	759	345	614	903	182	561	290	1028	415	688	760	346	613	904	181	562	289	1027	414	689	761	347	612	905	180	563	288	1026	1065	1130
25	90	132	845	708	996	474	323	557	899	600	251	133	844	709	997	475	322	556	898	601	250	134	843	710	998	476	321	555	897	602	249	1067	1132
23	88	1007	233	204	719	935	791	618	420	492	366	1006	232	205	718	934	790	619	421	493	367	1005	231	206	717	933	789	620	422	494	368	1069	1134
21	86	546	852	330	834	269	438	971	665	683	197	547	853	331	835	268	439	970	664	682	196	548	854	332	836	267	440	969	663	681	195	1071	1136
19	84	755	636	917	431	143	942	384	258	809	510	754	637	916	430	142	943	385	259	808	511	753	638	915	429	141	944	386	260	807	512	1073	1138
1	82	881	1014	593	222	528	737	780	186	395	449	880	1015	592	223	529	736	781	187	394	448	879	1016	591	224	530	735	782	188	393	447	1075	1156
1109	1045	240	467	521	215	816	629	863	312	978	744	241	466	520	214	817	628	862	313	979	745	242	465	519	213	818	627	861	314	980	746	112	48
1111	1047	798	539	485	870	377	294	726	953	161	582	799	538	484	871	376	295	727	952	160	583	800	537	483	872	375	296	728	951	159	584	110	46
1113	1049	654	341	989	503	672	150	305	827	456	888	655	340	988	502	673	151	304	826	457	889	656	339	987	501	674	152	303	825	458	890	108	44
1115	1051	359	168	276	647	960	575	402	701	924	773	358	169	277	646	961	574	403	700	925	772	357	170	278	645	962	573	404	699	926	771	106	42
1117	1053	413	690	762	348	611	906	179	564	287	1025	412	691	763	349	610	907	178	565	286	1024	411	692	764	350	609	908	177	566	285	1023	104	40
1119	1055	135	842	711	999	477	320	554	896	603	248	136	841	712	1000	478	319	553	895	604	247	137	840	713	1001	479	318	552	894	605	246	102	38
1121	1056	1004	230	207	716	932	788	621	423	495	369	1003	229	208	715	931	787	622	424	496	370	1002	228	209	714	930	786	623	425	497	371	101	36
1125	1061	549	855	333	837	266	441	968	662	680	194	550	856	334	838	265	442	967	661	679	193	551	857	335	839	264	443	966	660	678	192	96	32
1127	1062	752	639	914	428	140	945	387	261	806	513	751	640	913	427	139	946	388	262	805	514	750	641	912	426	138	947	389	263	804	515	95	30
1129	1064	878	1017	590	225	531	734	783	189	392	446	877	1018	589	226	532	733	784	190	391	445	876	1019	588	227	533	732	785	191	390	444	93	28
1131	1066	243	464	518	212	819	626	860	315	981	747	244	463	517	211	820	625	859	316	982	748	245	462	516	210	821	624	858	317	983	749	91	26
1133	1068	801	536	482	873	374	297	729	950	158	585	802	535	481	874	373	298	730	949	157	586	803	534	480	875	372	299	731	948	156	587	89	24
1135	1070	657	338	986	500	675	153	302	824	459	891	658	337	985	499	676	154	301	823	460	892	659	336	984	498	677	155	300	822	461	893	87	22
1137	1072	356	171	279	644	963	572	405	698	927	770	355	172	280	643	964	571	406	697	928	769	354	173	281	642	965	570	407	696	929	768	85	20
1139	1074	410	693	765	351	608	909	176	567	284	1022	409	694	766	352	607	910	175	568	283	1021	408	695	767	353	606	911	174	569	282	1020	83	18
1140	97	127	125	123	121	119	117	115	80	78	76	74	72	70	68	1029	1031	1033	1035	1037	1039	1041	1043	1076	1078	1080	1082	1084	1086	1088	1090	98	17
33	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1091	1093	1095	1097	1099	1101	1103	1105	1107	1141	1143	1145	1147	1149	1151	1153	1155	34

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 with following sums:

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 19669, \quad S_{32 \times 32} := 18512, \quad S_{30 \times 30} := 17355 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{10 \times 10} := 5785.$$

Blocks of order 10 are **magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

2.1.7 Seventh Way

Replace the entries 1 to 784 by 187 to 970 in Example 3.1 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{28 \times 28}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 given by

1123	1092	1094	1096	1098	1100	1102	1104	1106	1142	1144	1146	1148	1150	1152	1154	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	50	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	1124
49	1059	1030	1032	1034	1036	1038	1040	1042	1077	1079	1081	1083	1085	1087	1089	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	114	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	1060	1108
47	113	999	972	974	976	978	980	982	984	1016	1018	1020	1022	1024	1026	186	184	182	180	178	176	174	172	142	140	138	136	134	132	130	1000	1044	1110
45	111	171	481	774	187	872	482	773	188	871	483	772	189	870	484	771	190	869	485	770	191	868	486	769	192	867	487	768	193	866	986	1046	1112
43	109	169	284	775	578	677	283	776	577	678	282	777	576	679	281	778	575	680	280	779	574	681	279	780	573	682	278	781	572	683	988	1048	1114
41	107	167	970	285	676	383	969	286	675	384	968	287	674	385	967	288	673	386	966	289	672	387	965	290	671	388	964	291	670	389	990	1050	1116
39	105	165	579	480	873	382	580	479	874	381	581	478	875	380	582	477	876	379	583	476	877	378	584	475	878	377	585	474	879	376	992	1052	1118
37	103	163	488	767	194	865	489	766	195	864	490	765	196	863	491	764	197	862	492	763	198	861	493	762	199	860	494	761	200	859	994	1054	1120
35	100	161	277	782	571	684	276	783	570	685	275	784	569	686	274	785	568	687	273	786	567	688	272	787	566	689	271	788	565	690	996	1057	1122
31	99	159	963	292	669	390	962	293	668	391	961	294	667	392	960	295	666	393	959	296	665	394	958	297	664	395	957	298	663	396	998	1058	1126
29	94	155	586	473	880	375	587	472	881	374	588	471	882	373	589	470	883	372	590	469	884	371	591	468	885	370	592	467	886	369	1002	1063	1128
27	92	153	495	760	201	858	496	759	202	857	497	758	203	856	498	757	204	855	499	756	205	854	500	755	206	853	501	754	207	852	1004	1065	1130
25	90	151	270	789	564	691	269	790	563	692	268	791	562	693	267	792	561	694	266	793	560	695	265	794	559	696	264	795	558	697	1006	1067	1132
23	88	149	956	299	662	397	955	300	661	398	954	301	660	399	953	302	659	400	952	303	658	401	951	304	657	402	950	305	656	403	1008	1069	1134
21	86	147	593	466	887	368	594	465	888	367	595	464	889	366	596	463	890	365	597	462	891	364	598	461	892	363	599	460	893	362	1010	1071	1136
19	84	145	502	753	208	851	503	752	209	850	504	751	210	849	505	750	211	848	506	749	212	847	507	748	213	846	508	747	214	845	1012	1073	1138
1	82	129	263	796	557	698	262	797	556	699	261	798	555	700	260	799	554	701	259	800	553	702	258	801	552	703	257	802	551	704	1028	1075	1156
1109	1045	987	949	306	655	404	948	307	654	405	947	308	653	406	946	309	652	407	945	310	651	408	944	311	650	409	943	312	649	410	170	112	48
1111	1047	989	600	459	894	361	601	458	895	360	602	457	896	359	603	456	897	358	604	455	898	357	605	454	899	356	606	453	900	355	168	110	46
1113	1049	991	509	746	215	844	510	745	216	843	511	744	217	842	512	743	218	841	513	742	219	840	514	741	220	839	515	740	221	838	166	108	44
1115	1051	993	256	803	550	705	255	804	549	706	254	805	548	707	253	806	547	708	252	807	546	709	251	808	545	710	250	809	544	711	164	106	42
1117	1053	995	942	313	648	411	941	314	647	412	940	315	646	413	939	316	645	414	938	317	644	415	937	318	643	416	936	319	642	417	162	104	40
1119	1055	997	607	452	901	354	608	451	902	353	609	450	903	352	610	449	904	351	611	448	905	350	612	447	906	349	613	446	907	348	160	102	38
1121	1056	1001	516	739	222	837	517	738	223	836	518	737	224	835	519	736	225	834	520	735	226	833	521	734	227	832	522	733	228	831	156	101	36
1125	1061	1003	249	810	543	712	248	811	542	713	247	812	541	714	246	813	540	715	245	814	539	716	244	815	538	717	243	816	537	718	154	96	32
1127	1062	1005	935	320	641	418	934	321	640	419	933	322	639	420	932	323	638	421	931	324	637	422	930	325	636	423	929	326	635	424	152	95	30
1129	1064	1007	614	445	908	347	615	444	909	346	616	443	910	345	617	442	911	344	618	441	912	343	619	440	913	342	620	439	914	341	150	93	28
1131	1066	1009	523	732	229	830	524	731	230	829	525	730	231	828	526	729	232	827	527	728	233	826	528	727	234	825	529	726	235	824	148	91	26
1133	1068	1011	242	817	536	719	241	818	535	720	240	819	534	721	239	820	533	722	238	821	532	723	237	822	531	724	236	823	530	725	146	89	24
1135	1070	1013	928	327	634	425	927	328	633	426	926	329	632	427	925	330	631	428	924	331	630	429	923	332	629	430	922	333	628	431	144	87	22
1137	1072	1014	621	438	915	340	622	437	916	339	623	436	917	338	624	435	918	337	625	434	919	336	626	433	920	335	627	432	921	334	143	85	20
1139	1074	157	185	183	181	179	177	175	173	141	139	137	135	133	131	971	973	975	977	979	981	983	985	1015	1017	1019	1021	1023	1025	1027	158	83	18
1140	97	127	125	123	121	119	117	115	80	78	76	74	72	70	68	1029	1031	1033	1035	1037	1039	1041	1043	1076	1078	1080	1082	1084	1086	1088	1090	98	17
33	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1091	1093	1095	1097	1099	1101	1103	1105	1107	1141	1143	1145	1147	1149	1151	1153	1155	34

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34, where the magic square of order 28 is **pandiagonal** with the following sums:

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 19669, \quad S_{32 \times 32} := 18512, \quad S_{30 \times 30} := 17355 \quad S_{28 \times 28} := 16198 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{4 \times 4} := 2314.$$

Blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

2.1.8 Eight Way

Replace the entries 1 to 784 by 187 to 970 in Example 3.2 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{28 \times 28}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 given by

1123	1092	1094	1096	1098	1100	1102	1104	1106	1142	1144	1146	1148	1150	1152	1154	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	50	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	1124
49	1059	1030	1032	1034	1036	1038	1040	1042	1077	1079	1081	1083	1085	1087	1089	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	114	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	1060	1108
47	113	999	972	974	976	978	980	982	984	1016	1018	1020	1022	1024	1026	186	184	182	180	178	176	174	172	142	140	138	136	134	132	130	1000	1044	1110
45	111	171	193	321	449	577	705	833	961	198	326	454	582	710	838	966	187	315	443	571	699	827	955	200	328	456	584	712	840	968	986	1046	1112
43	109	169	817	945	289	305	433	561	689	822	950	294	310	438	566	694	811	939	283	299	427	555	683	824	952	296	312	440	568	696	988	1048	1114
41	107	167	545	673	801	929	273	401	417	550	678	806	934	278	406	422	539	667	795	923	267	395	411	552	680	808	936	280	408	424	990	1050	1116
39	105	165	385	513	529	657	785	913	257	390	518	534	662	790	918	262	379	507	523	651	779	907	251	392	520	536	664	792	920	264	992	1052	1118
37	103	163	897	241	369	497	625	641	769	902	246	374	502	630	646	774	891	235	363	491	619	635	763	904	248	376	504	632	648	776	994	1054	1120
35	100	161	737	753	881	225	353	481	609	742	758	886	230	358	486	614	731	747	875	219	347	475	603	744	760	888	232	360	488	616	996	1057	1122
31	99	159	465	593	721	849	865	209	337	470	598	726	854	870	214	342	459	587	715	843	859	203	331	472	600	728	856	872	216	344	998	1058	1126
29	94	155	188	316	444	572	700	828	956	199	327	455	583	711	839	967	194	322	450	578	706	834	962	197	325	453	581	709	837	965	1002	1063	1128
27	92	153	812	940	284	300	428	556	684	823	951	295	311	439	567	695	818	946	290	306	434	562	690	821	949	293	309	437	565	693	1004	1065	1130
25	90	151	540	668	796	924	268	396	412	551	679	807	935	279	407	423	546	674	802	930	274	402	418	549	677	805	933	277	405	421	1006	1067	1132
23	88	149	380	508	524	652	780	908	252	391	519	535	663	791	919	263	386	514	530	658	786	914	258	389	517	533	661	789	917	261	1008	1069	1134
21	86	147	892	236	364	492	620	636	764	903	247	375	503	631	647	775	898	242	370	498	626	642	770	901	245	373	501	629	645	773	1010	1071	1136
19	84	145	732	748	876	220	348	476	604	743	759	887	231	359	487	615	738	754	882	226	354	482	610	741	757	885	229	357	485	613	1012	1073	1138
1	82	129	460	588	716	844	860	204	332	471	599	727	855	871	215	343	466	594	722	850	866	210	338	469	597	725	853	869	213	341	1028	1075	1156
1109	1045	987	202	330	458	586	714	842	970	189	317	445	573	701	829	957	196	324	452	580	708	836	964	191	319	447	575	703	831	959	170	112	48
1111	1047	989	826	954	298	314	442	570	698	813	941	285	301	429	557	685	820	948	292	308	436	564	692	815	943	287	303	431	559	687	168	110	46
1113	1049	991	554	682	810	938	282	410	426	541	669	797	925	269	397	413	548	676	804	932	276	404	420	543	671	799	927	271	399	415	166	108	44
1115	1051	993	394	522	538	666	794	922	266	381	509	525	653	781	909	253	388	516	532	660	788	916	260	383	511	527	655	783	911	255	164	106	42
1117	1053	995	906	250	378	506	634	650	778	893	237	365	493	621	637	765	900	244	372	500	628	644	772	895	239	367	495	623	639	767	162	104	40
1119	1055	997	746	762	890	234	362	490	618	733	749	877	221	349	477	605	740	756	884	228	356	484	612	735	751	879	223	351	479	607	160	102	38
1121	1056	1001	474	602	730	858	874	218	346	461	589	717	845	861	205	333	468	596	724	852	868	212	340	463	591	719	847	863	207	335	156	101	36
1125	1061	1003	195	323	451	579	707	835	963	192	320	448	576	704	832	960	201	329	457	585	713	841	969	190	318	446	574	702	830	958	154	96	32
1127	1062	1005	819	947	291	307	435	563	691	816	944	288	304	432	560	688	825	953	297	313	441	569	697	814	942	286	302	430	558	686	152	95	30
1129	1064	1007	547	675	803	931	275	403	419	544	672	800	928	272	400	416	553	681	809	937	281	409	425	542	670	798	926	270	398	414	150	93	28
1131	1066	1009	387	515	531	659	787	915	259	384	512	528	656	784	912	256	393	521	537	665	793	921	265	382	510	526	654	782	910	254	148	91	26
1133	1068	1011	899	243	371	499	627	643	771	896	240	368	496	624	640	768	905	249	377	505	633	649	777	894	238	366	494	622	638	766	146	89	24
1135	1070	1013	739	755	883	227	355	483	611	736	752	880	224	352	480	608	745	761	889	233	361	489	617	734	750	878	222	350	478	606	144	87	22
1137	1072	1014	467	595	723	851	867	211	339	464	592	720	848	864	208	336	473	601	729	857	873	217	345	462	590	718	846	862	206	334	143	85	20
1139	1074	157	185	183	181	179	177	175	173	141	139	137	135	133	131	971	973	975	977	979	981	983	985	1015	1017	1019	1021	1023	1025	1027	158	83	18
1140	97	127	125	123	121	119	117	115	80	78	76	74	72	70	68	1029	1031	1033	1035	1037	1039	1041	1043	1076	1078	1080	1082	1084	1086	1088	1090	98	17
33	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1091	1093	1095	1097	1099	1101	1103	1105	1107	1141	1143	1145	1147	1149	1151	1153	1155	34

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34, where magic square of order 28 is **pandiagonal** with following sums:

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 19669, \quad S_{32 \times 32} := 18512, \quad S_{30 \times 30} := 17355 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{28 \times 28} := 16198.$$

Blocks of order 7×7 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **different magic sums**.

2.1.9 Ninth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 784 by 187 to 970 in Example 3.4 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{28 \times 28}$ appearing in Example 2.1, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 given by

1123	1092	1094	1096	1098	1100	1102	1104	1106	1142	1144	1146	1148	1150	1152	1154	66	64	62	60	58	56	54	52	50	16	14	12	10	8	6	4	2	1124
49	1059	1030	1032	1034	1036	1038	1040	1042	1077	1079	1081	1083	1085	1087	1089	128	126	124	122	120	118	116	114	81	79	77	75	73	71	69	67	1060	1108
47	113	999	972	974	976	978	980	982	984	1016	1018	1020	1022	1024	1026	186	184	182	180	178	176	174	172	142	140	138	136	134	132	130	1000	1044	1110
45	111	171	187	563	947	634	738	498	418	314	251	819	770	898	683	379	188	564	948	633	737	497	417	313	252	820	769	897	684	380	986	1046	1112
43	109	169	771	250	626	890	938	691	531	651	202	395	466	515	338	835	772	249	625	889	937	692	532	652	201	396	465	516	337	836	988	1048	1114
41	107	167	690	834	307	731	874	435	506	210	371	290	571	579	779	922	689	833	308	732	873	436	505	209	372	289	572	580	780	921	990	1050	1116
39	105	165	946	627	786	370	803	643	203	491	322	866	275	570	746	451	945	628	785	369	804	644	204	492	321	865	276	569	745	452	992	1052	1118
37	103	163	842	522	403	234	667	530	299	587	715	434	875	283	930	778	841	521	404	233	668	529	300	588	716	433	876	284	929	777	994	1054	1120
35	100	161	602	226	539	331	267	850	899	802	963	482	362	722	419	635	601	225	540	332	268	849	900	801	964	481	361	721	420	636	996	1057	1122
31	99	159	259	323	714	411	195	795	970	843	906	554	674	387	474	594	260	324	713	412	196	796	969	844	905	553	673	388	473	593	998	1058	1126
29	94	155	363	443	467	546	330	955	794	907	858	659	706	194	595	282	364	444	468	545	329	956	793	908	857	660	705	193	596	281	1002	1063	1128
27	92	153	306	355	426	475	562	914	851	962	787	611	211	658	274	707	305	356	425	476	561	913	852	961	788	612	212	657	273	708	1004	1065	1130
25	90	151	458	762	810	291	483	378	603	555	666	730	915	354	227	867	457	761	809	292	484	377	604	556	665	729	916	353	228	868	1006	1067	1132
23	88	149	507	931	883	642	459	258	723	394	523	242	610	755	826	346	508	932	884	641	460	257	724	393	524	241	609	756	825	345	1008	1069	1134
21	86	147	739	882	218	827	754	618	650	243	499	923	339	427	402	578	740	881	217	828	753	617	649	244	500	924	340	428	401	577	1010	1071	1136
19	84	145	891	699	675	954	410	315	266	442	586	747	514	818	547	235	892	700	676	953	409	316	265	441	585	748	513	817	548	236	1012	1073	1138
1	82	129	538	682	298	763	619	219	386	698	450	347	811	939	859	490	537	681	297	764	620	220	385	697	449	348	812	940	860	489	1028	1075	1156
1109	1045	987	189	565	949	632	736	496	416	312	253	821	768	896	685	381	190	566	950	631	735	495	415	311	254	822	767	895	686	382	170	112	48
1111	1047	989	773	248	624	888	936	693	533	653	200	397	464	517	336	837	774	247	623	887	935	694	534	654	199	398	463	518	335	838	168	110	46
1113	1049	991	688	832	309	733	872	437	504	208	373	288	573	581	781	920	687	831	310	734	871	438	503	207	374	287	574	582	782	919	166	108	44
1115	1051	993	944	629	784	368	805	645	205	493	320	864	277	568	744	453	943	630	783	367	806	646	206	494	319	863	278	567	743	454	164	106	42
1117	1053	995	840	520	405	232	669	528	301	589	717	432	877	285	928	776	839	519	406	231	670	527	302	590	718	431	878	286	927	775	162	104	40
1119	1055	997	600	224	541	333	269	848	901	800	965	480	360	720	421	637	599	223	542	334	270	847	902	799	966	479	359	719	422	638	160	102	38
1121	1056	1001	261	325	712	413	197	797	968	845	904	552	672	389	472	592	262	326	711	414	198	798	967	846	903	551	671	390	471	591	156	101	36
1125	1061	1003	365	445	469	544	328	957	792	909	856	661	704	192	597	280	366	446	470	543	327	958	791	910	855	662	703	191	598	279	154	96	32
1127	1062	1005	304	357	424	477	560	912	853	960	789	613	213	656	272	709	303	358	423	478	559	911	854	959	790	614	214	655	271	710	152	95	30
1129	1064	1007	456	760	808	293	485	376	605	557	664	728	917	352	229	869	455	759	807	294	486	375	606	558	663	727	918	351	230	870	150	93	28
1131	1066	1009	509	933	885	640	461	256	725	392	525	240	608	757	824	344	510	934	886	639	462	255	726	391	526	239	607	758	823	343	148	91	26
1133	1068	1011	741	880	216	829	752	616	648	245	501	925	341	429	400	576	742	879	215	830	751	615	647	246	502	926	342	430	399	575	146	89	24
1135	1070	1013	893	701	677	952	408	317	264	440	584	749	512	816	549	237	894	702	678	951	407	318	263	439	583	750	511	815	550	238	144	87	22
1137	1072	1014	536	680	296	765	621	221	384	696	448	349	813	941	861	488	535	679	295	766	622	222	383	695	447	350	814	942	862	487	143	85	20
1139	1074	157	185	183	181	179	177	175	173	141	139	137	135	133	131	971	973	975	977	979	981	983	985	1015	1017	1019	1021	1023	1025	1027	158	83	18
1140	97	127	125	123	121	119	117	115	80	78	76	74	72	70	68	1029	1031	1033	1035	1037	1039	1041	1043	1076	1078	1080	1082	1084	1086	1088	1090	98	17
33	65	63	61	59	57	55	53	51	15	13	11	9	7	5	3	1091	1093	1095	1097	1099	1101	1103	1105	1107	1141	1143	1145	1147	1149	1151	1153	1155	34

Thus, we have a **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 with following sums:

$$S_{34 \times 34} := 19669, \quad S_{32 \times 32} := 18512, \quad S_{30 \times 30} := 17355 \quad S_{28 \times 28} := 16198 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{14 \times 14} := 8099.$$

Blocks of order 14 are **magic squares with equal magic sums**.

Summarizing, we have following result:

Result 2.1. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 34 in nine different ways. The blocks are considered as given below:*

- (i) Pandiagonal magic square of 32, where blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums**;*
- (ii) Pandiagonal bimagic square of 32, where blocks of order 8 are **pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums**. Also the magic squares of order 8 are either **bimagic or semi-bimagic squares with different bimagic or semi-bimagic sums**;*
- (iii) Magic square of 30, where blocks of order 3 are **magic squares with different magic sums**;*
- (iv) Magic square of 30, where blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums**;*
- (v) Magic square of 30, where blocks of order 6 are **magic squares with equal magic sums**;*
- (vi) Magic square of 30, where blocks of order 10 are **magic squares with equal magic sums**;*
- (vii) Pandiagonal magic square of 28, where blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums**;*
- (viii) Pandiagonal magic square of 28, where blocks of order 7 are **pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums**;*
- (ix) Magic square of 28, where blocks of order 14 are **magic squares with equal magic sums**.*

2.2 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of order 37

Example 2.2. *Let's consider a **bordered magic square of order 37** given by*

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{5 \times 5} &:= \{673, 674, \dots, 679, 680, D_{3 \times 3}, 690, 691, \dots, 696, 697\}; & S_{5 \times 5} &:= 3425 \\
 D_{7 \times 7} &:= \{661, 662, \dots, 671, 672, D_{5 \times 5}, 698, 699, \dots, 708, 709\}; & S_{7 \times 7} &:= 4795 \\
 D_{9 \times 9} &:= \{645, 646, \dots, 659, 660, D_{7 \times 7}, 710, 711, \dots, 724, 725\}; & S_{9 \times 9} &:= 6195 \\
 D_{11 \times 11} &:= \{625, 626, \dots, 643, 644, D_{9 \times 9}, 726, 727, \dots, 744, 745\}; & S_{11 \times 11} &:= 7535 \\
 D_{13 \times 13} &:= \{601, 602, \dots, 623, 624, D_{11 \times 11}, 746, 747, \dots, 768, 769\}; & S_{13 \times 13} &:= 8905 \\
 D_{15 \times 15} &:= \{573, 574, \dots, 599, 600, D_{13 \times 13}, 770, 771, \dots, 796, 797\}; & S_{15 \times 15} &:= 10275 \\
 D_{17 \times 17} &:= \{541, 542, \dots, 571, 572, D_{15 \times 15}, 798, 799, \dots, 828, 829\}; & S_{17 \times 17} &:= 11645 \\
 D_{19 \times 19} &:= \{505, 506, \dots, 539, 540, D_{17 \times 17}, 830, 831, \dots, 864, 865\}; & S_{19 \times 19} &:= 13015 \\
 D_{21 \times 21} &:= \{465, 466, \dots, 503, 504, D_{19 \times 19}, 866, 867, \dots, 904, 905\}; & S_{21 \times 21} &:= 14385 \\
 D_{23 \times 23} &:= \{421, 422, \dots, 463, 464, D_{21 \times 21}, 906, 907, \dots, 948, 949\}; & S_{23 \times 23} &:= 15755 \\
 D_{25 \times 25} &:= \{373, 374, \dots, 419, 420, D_{23 \times 23}, 950, 951, \dots, 996, 997\}; & S_{25 \times 25} &:= 17125 \\
 D_{27 \times 27} &:= \{321, 322, \dots, 371, 372, D_{25 \times 25}, 998, 999, \dots, 1048, 1049\}; & S_{27 \times 27} &:= 18495 \\
 D_{29 \times 29} &:= \{265, 266, \dots, 319, 320, D_{27 \times 27}, 1050, 1051, \dots, 1104, 1105\}; & S_{29 \times 29} &:= 19865 \\
 D_{31 \times 31} &:= \{205, 206, \dots, 263, 264, D_{29 \times 29}, 1106, 1107, \dots, 1164, 1165\}; & S_{31 \times 31} &:= 21235 \\
 D_{33 \times 33} &:= \{141, 142, \dots, 203, 204, D_{31 \times 31}, 1166, 1167, \dots, 1228, 1229\}; & S_{33 \times 33} &:= 22605 \\
 D_{35 \times 35} &:= \{7374, \dots, 59, 140, D_{33 \times 33}, 1230, 1231, \dots, 1295, 1297\}; & S_{35 \times 35} &:= 23975 \\
 D_{37 \times 37} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 71, 72, D_{35 \times 35}, 1298, 1999, \dots, 1268, 1369\}; & S_{37 \times 37} &:= 25345.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are four different ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 37. These are based on the magic squares of orders 35 and 33 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.14, 3.15, 3.16 and 3.17.

2.2.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1225 by 73 to 1297 in Example 3.16 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{35 \times 35}$ appearing in Example 2.2, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 37 given by

$$S_{37 \times 37} := 25345, \quad S_{35 \times 35} := 23975 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{5 \times 5} := 3425.$$

Blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

2.2.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1225 by 73 to 1297 in Example 3.17 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{35 \times 35}$ appearing in Example 2.2, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 37 given by

$$S_{37 \times 37} := 25345, \quad S_{35 \times 35} := 23975 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{7 \times 7} := 4795.$$

Blocks of order 7 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

2.2.3 Third Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1089 by 141 to 1129 in Example 3.14 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{33 \times 33}$ appearing in Example 2.2, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 37 given by

$$S_{37 \times 37} := 25345, \quad S_{35 \times 35} := 23975, \quad S_{33 \times 33} := 22605 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{3 \times 3} := 2055$$

Blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** with **equal semi-magic sums**.

2.2.4 Forth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1089 by 141 to 1129 in Example 3.15 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{33 \times 33}$ appearing in Example 2.2, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 37 given by

$$S_{37 \times 37} := 25345, \quad S_{35 \times 35} := 23975, \quad S_{33 \times 33} := 22605 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{11 \times 11} := 7535$$

Blocks of order 11 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**, i.e., 7535.

Summarizing, we have following result:

Result 2.2. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 37 in four different ways. The blocks considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of 35, where blocks of order 5 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**;*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of 35, where blocks of order 7 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**;*
- (iii) *Pandiagonal magic square of 33, where blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** with **equal semi-magic sums**;*
- (iv) *Pandiagonal magic square of 33, where blocks of order 11 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.*

2.3 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of order 38

Example 2.3. *Let's consider a **bordered magic square** of order 38 given by*

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{4 \times 4} &:= \{715, 716, \dots, 144, 729, 730\}; & S_{4 \times 4} &:= 2890 \\
 D_{6 \times 6} &:= \{705, 706, \dots, 713, 714, D_{4 \times 4}, 731, 732, \dots, 739, 740\}; & S_{6 \times 6} &:= 4335 \\
 D_{8 \times 8} &:= \{691, 692, \dots, 703, 704, D_{6 \times 6}, 741, 742, \dots, 753, 754\}; & S_{8 \times 8} &:= 5780 \\
 D_{10 \times 10} &:= \{673, 674, \dots, 689, 690, D_{8 \times 8}, 755, 756, \dots, 751, 772\}; & S_{10 \times 10} &:= 7225 \\
 D_{12 \times 12} &:= \{651, 652, \dots, 671, 672, D_{10 \times 10}, 773, 774, \dots, 793, 794\}; & S_{12 \times 12} &:= 8670 \\
 D_{14 \times 14} &:= \{625, 626, \dots, 649, 650, D_{12 \times 12}, 795, 809, \dots, 819, 820\}; & S_{14 \times 14} &:= 10115 \\
 D_{16 \times 16} &:= \{595, 596, \dots, 623, 624, D_{14 \times 14}, 821, 822, \dots, 849, 850\}; & S_{16 \times 16} &:= 11560 \\
 D_{18 \times 18} &:= \{561, 562, \dots, 593, 594, D_{16 \times 16}, 851, 852, \dots, 883, 884\}; & S_{18 \times 18} &:= 13005 \\
 D_{20 \times 20} &:= \{523, 524, \dots, 559, 560, D_{18 \times 18}, 885, 886, \dots, 921, 922\}; & S_{20 \times 20} &:= 14450 \\
 D_{22 \times 22} &:= \{481, 482, \dots, 521, 522, D_{20 \times 20}, 923, 924, \dots, 963, 964\}; & S_{22 \times 22} &:= 15895 \\
 D_{24 \times 24} &:= \{435, 436, \dots, 479, 480, D_{22 \times 22}, 965, 966, \dots, 1009, 1010\}; & S_{24 \times 24} &:= 17340 \\
 D_{26 \times 26} &:= \{385, 386, \dots, 433, 434, D_{24 \times 24}, 1011, 1012, \dots, 1055, 1060\}; & S_{26 \times 26} &:= 18785 \\
 D_{28 \times 28} &:= \{331, 332, \dots, 383, 384, D_{26 \times 26}, 1061, 1058, \dots, 1113, 1114\}; & S_{28 \times 28} &:= 20230 \\
 D_{30 \times 30} &:= \{273, 274, \dots, 329, 330, D_{28 \times 28}, 1115, 1116, \dots, 1149, 1172\}; & S_{30 \times 30} &:= 21675 \\
 D_{32 \times 32} &:= \{211, 212, \dots, 271, 272, D_{30 \times 30}, 1173, 1174, \dots, 1207, 1234\}; & S_{32 \times 32} &:= 23120 \\
 D_{34 \times 34} &:= \{145, 146, \dots, 209, 210, D_{32 \times 32}, 1235, 1236, \dots, 1299, 1300\}; & S_{34 \times 34} &:= 24565 \\
 D_{36 \times 36} &:= \{75, 76, \dots, 143, 144, D_{34 \times 34}, 1301, 1302, \dots, 1369, 1370\}; & S_{36 \times 36} &:= 26010 \\
 D_{38 \times 38} &:= \{1, 2, \dots, 73, 74, D_{36 \times 36}, 1371, 1372, \dots, 1143, 1444\}; & S_{38 \times 38} &:= 27455.
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are six ways of writing **block-bordered** magic square of order 38. These are based on the magic squares of order 36 given in Appendix 3 as Examples 3.18, 3.21, 3.22, 3.23, 3.25 and 3.26.

2.3.1 First Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1296 by 75 to 1370 in Example 3.18 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{36 \times 36}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 38 given by

$$S_{38 \times 38} := 27455 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{36 \times 36} := 26010$$

Blocks of order 3 are **magic squares** with **different magic sums**.

2.3.2 Second Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1296 by 75 to 1370 in Example 3.21 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{36 \times 36}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 38 given by

$$S_{38 \times 38} := 27455, \quad S_{36 \times 36} := 26010, \quad \text{and} \quad S_{4 \times 4} := 2890$$

Blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

2.3.3 Third Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1296 by 75 to 1370 in Example 3.22 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{36 \times 36}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 38 given by

$$S_{38 \times 38} := 27455, \quad S_{36 \times 36} := 26010, \quad \text{and} \quad S_{6 \times 6} := 4335$$

Blocks of order 6 are **magic squares** with **equal magic sums**.

2.3.4 Forth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1296 by 75 to 1370 in Example 3.23 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{36 \times 36}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 38 given by

$$S_{38 \times 38} := 27455 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{36 \times 36} := 26010$$

Blocks of order 9 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **different magic sums**. Moreover, in each block of order 9, the blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** with **equal semi-magic sums**.

2.3.5 Fifth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1296 by 75 to 1370 in Example 3.25 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{36 \times 36}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 38 given by

$$S_{38 \times 38} := 27455, \quad S_{36 \times 36} := 26010, \quad \text{and} \quad S_{12 \times 12} : 7782$$

Blocks of order 12 are **pandiagonal magic squares** with **equal magic sums**. Moreover, the blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** with **different semi-magic sums**.

2.3.6 Sixth Way

Replace the entries 1 to 1296 by 75 to 1370 in Example 3.26 given in Appendix 3, and then replace it in $D_{36 \times 36}$ appearing in Example 2.3, we get a **block-bordered** magic square of order 38 given by

$$S_{38 \times 38} := 27455 \quad \text{and} \quad S_{36 \times 36} := 26010$$

Sum of 36 entries in each block of order 6 are of equal sums as of magic square of order 36. Moreover, the magic square of order 36 is **pandiagonal** and **bimagic** with **bimagic sum** $Sb_{36 \times 36} := 20178726$.

Summarizing, we have following result:

Result 2.3. *We have written **block-bordered** magic square of order 38 in six different ways. The blocks considered are as given below:*

- (i) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 36, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares with different magic sums;*
- (ii) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 36, where blocks of order 4 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums;*
- (iii) *Magic square of order 36, where blocks of order 6 are magic squares with equal magic sums;*
- (iv) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 36, where blocks of order 9 are pandiagonal magic squares with different magic sums. Moreover, each block of order 9×9 is formed by semi-magic squares of order 3 with equal semi-magic sums;*
- (v) *Pandiagonal magic square of order 36, where blocks of order 12 are pandiagonal magic squares with equal magic sums. Moreover, each block of order 3×3 is semi-magic square with different semi-magic sums.*
- (vi) *Pandiagonal bimagic square of order 36, where sum of 36 entries of blocks of order 6 are the same as of magic square of order 36. This magic square is constructed by Su Maoting [2].*

3 Appendix: Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares

This section brings **block-wise magic squares** of orders 28, 30, 33, 35 and 36. These are already constructed by author in previous works [28, 29, 30, 31]. The aim rewriting them is that we shall use them in constructions of **block-bordered magic squares** of orders 34, 37 and 38.

3.1 Magic Square of Order 28

In this subsection, we shall present three different ways of writing **pandiagonal** magic square of order 28. One as 4×7 , i.e., magic square formed by 49 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. Second as 7×4 , i.e., magic square formed by 16 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 7. Third as, 14×2 , i.e., magic square formed by 4 blocks of equal magic sums of order 14. In the first two cases the magic squares of order 28 are **pandiagonal**, while in the third case, it is just a magic square.

3.1.1 First Approach: 49 Blocks of Order 4

Example 3.1. *A pandiagonal magic square of order 28 formed by 49 blocks of pandiagonal magic squares of order 4 constructed according to Example 1.2 is given by*

		10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	
	295	588	1	686	296	587	2	685	297	586	3	684	298	585	4	683	299	584	5	682	300	583	6	681	301	582	7	680	10990
10990	98	589	392	491	97	590	391	492	96	591	390	493	95	592	389	494	94	593	388	495	93	594	387	496	92	595	386	497	10990
10990	784	99	490	197	783	100	489	198	782	101	488	199	781	102	487	200	780	103	486	201	779	104	485	202	778	105	484	203	10990
10990	393	294	687	196	394	293	688	195	395	292	689	194	396	291	690	193	397	290	691	192	398	289	692	191	399	288	693	190	10990
10990	302	581	8	679	303	580	9	678	304	579	10	677	305	578	11	676	306	577	12	675	307	576	13	674	308	575	14	673	10990
10990	91	596	385	498	90	597	384	499	89	598	383	500	88	599	382	501	87	600	381	502	86	601	380	503	85	602	379	504	10990
10990	777	106	483	204	776	107	482	205	775	108	481	206	774	109	480	207	773	110	479	208	772	111	478	209	771	112	477	210	10990
10990	400	287	694	189	401	286	695	188	402	285	696	187	403	284	697	186	404	283	698	185	405	282	699	184	406	281	700	183	10990
10990	309	574	15	672	310	573	16	671	311	572	17	670	312	571	18	669	313	570	19	668	314	569	20	667	315	568	21	666	10990
10990	84	603	378	505	83	604	377	506	82	605	376	507	81	606	375	508	80	607	374	509	79	608	373	510	78	609	372	511	10990
10990	770	113	476	211	769	114	475	212	768	115	474	213	767	116	473	214	766	117	472	215	765	118	471	216	764	119	470	217	10990
10990	407	280	701	182	408	279	702	181	409	278	703	180	410	277	704	179	411	276	705	178	412	275	706	177	413	274	707	176	10990
10990	316	567	22	665	317	566	23	664	318	565	24	663	319	564	25	662	320	563	26	661	321	562	27	660	322	561	28	659	10990
10990	77	610	371	512	76	611	370	513	75	612	369	514	74	613	368	515	73	614	367	516	72	615	366	517	71	616	365	518	10990
10990	763	120	469	218	762	121	468	219	761	122	467	220	760	123	466	221	759	124	465	222	758	125	464	223	757	126	463	224	10990
10990	414	273	708	175	415	272	709	174	416	271	710	173	417	270	711	172	418	269	712	171	419	268	713	170	420	267	714	169	10990
10990	323	560	29	658	324	559	30	657	325	558	31	656	326	557	32	655	327	556	33	654	328	555	34	653	329	554	35	652	10990
10990	70	617	364	519	69	618	363	520	68	619	362	521	67	620	361	522	66	621	360	523	65	622	359	524	64	623	358	525	10990
10990	756	127	462	225	755	128	461	226	754	129	460	227	753	130	459	228	752	131	458	229	751	132	457	230	750	133	456	231	10990
10990	421	266	715	168	422	265	716	167	423	264	717	166	424	263	718	165	425	262	719	164	426	261	720	163	427	260	721	162	10990
10990	330	553	36	651	331	552	37	650	332	551	38	649	333	550	39	648	334	549	40	647	335	548	41	646	336	547	42	645	10990
10990	63	624	357	526	62	625	356	527	61	626	355	528	60	627	354	529	59	628	353	530	58	629	352	531	57	630	351	532	10990
10990	749	134	455	232	748	135	454	233	747	136	453	234	746	137	452	235	745	138	451	236	744	139	450	237	743	140	449	238	10990
10990	428	259	722	161	429	258	723	160	430	257	724	159	431	256	725	158	432	255	726	157	433	254	727	156	434	253	728	155	10990
10990	337	546	43	644	338	545	44	643	339	544	45	642	340	543	46	641	341	542	47	640	342	541	48	639	343	540	49	638	10990
10990	56	631	350	533	55	632	349	534	54	633	348	535	53	634	347	536	52	635	346	537	51	636	345	538	50	637	344	539	10990
10990	742	141	448	239	741	142	447	240	740	143	446	241	739	144	445	242	738	145	444	243	737	146	443	244	736	147	442	245	10990
10990	435	252	729	154	436	251	730	153	437	250	731	152	438	249	732	151	439	248	733	150	440	247	734	149	441	246	735	148	10990
	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990

In this case, all the 49 blocks of order 4 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with equal magic sums, $S_{4 \times 4} := 1570$

3.1.2 Second Approach: 16 Blocks of Order 7

Example 3.2. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 28 formed by 16 blocks of *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 7 constructed according to Example 1.5 is given by

		10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990
	7	135	263	391	519	647	775	12	140	268	396	524	652	780	1	129	257	385	513	641	769	14	142	270	398	526	654	782	10990		
10990	631	759	103	119	247	375	503	636	764	108	124	252	380	508	625	753	97	113	241	369	497	638	766	110	126	254	382	510	10990		
10990	359	487	615	743	87	215	231	364	492	620	748	92	220	236	353	481	609	737	81	209	225	366	494	622	750	94	222	238	10990		
10990	199	327	343	471	599	727	71	204	332	348	476	604	732	76	193	321	337	465	593	721	65	206	334	350	478	606	734	78	10990		
10990	711	55	183	311	439	455	583	716	60	188	316	444	460	588	705	49	177	305	433	449	577	718	62	190	318	446	462	590	10990		
10990	551	567	695	39	167	295	423	556	572	700	44	172	300	428	545	561	689	33	161	289	417	558	574	702	46	174	302	430	10990		
10990	279	407	535	663	679	23	151	284	412	540	668	684	28	156	273	401	529	657	673	17	145	286	414	542	670	686	30	158	10990		
10990	2	130	258	386	514	642	770	13	141	269	397	525	653	781	8	136	264	392	520	648	776	11	139	267	395	523	651	779	10990		
10990	626	754	98	114	242	370	498	637	765	109	125	253	381	509	632	760	104	120	248	376	504	635	763	107	123	251	379	507	10990		
10990	354	482	610	738	82	210	226	365	493	621	749	93	221	237	360	488	616	744	88	216	232	363	491	619	747	91	219	235	10990		
10990	194	322	338	466	594	722	66	205	333	349	477	605	733	77	200	328	344	472	600	728	72	203	331	347	475	603	731	75	10990		
10990	706	50	178	306	434	450	578	717	61	189	317	445	461	589	712	56	184	312	440	456	584	715	59	187	315	443	459	587	10990		
10990	546	562	690	34	162	290	418	557	573	701	45	173	301	429	552	568	696	40	168	296	424	555	571	699	43	171	299	427	10990		
10990	274	402	530	658	674	18	146	285	413	541	669	685	29	157	280	408	536	664	680	24	152	283	411	539	667	683	27	155	10990		
10990	16	144	272	400	528	656	784	3	131	259	387	515	643	771	10	138	266	394	522	650	778	5	133	261	389	517	645	773	10990		
10990	640	768	112	128	256	384	512	627	755	99	115	243	371	499	634	762	106	122	250	378	506	629	757	101	117	245	373	501	10990		
10990	368	496	624	752	96	224	240	355	483	611	739	83	211	227	362	490	618	746	90	218	234	357	485	613	741	85	213	229	10990		
10990	208	336	352	480	608	736	80	195	323	339	467	595	723	67	202	330	346	474	602	730	74	197	325	341	469	597	725	69	10990		
10990	720	64	192	320	448	464	592	707	51	179	307	435	451	579	714	58	186	314	442	458	586	709	53	181	309	437	453	581	10990		
10990	560	576	704	48	176	304	432	547	563	691	35	163	291	419	554	570	698	42	170	298	426	549	565	693	37	165	293	421	10990		
10990	288	416	544	672	688	32	160	275	403	531	659	675	19	147	282	410	538	666	682	26	154	277	405	533	661	677	21	149	10990		
10990	9	137	265	393	521	649	777	6	134	262	390	518	646	774	15	143	271	399	527	655	783	4	132	260	388	516	644	772	10990		
10990	633	761	105	121	249	377	505	630	758	102	118	246	374	502	639	767	111	127	255	383	511	628	756	100	116	244	372	500	10990		
10990	361	489	617	745	89	217	233	358	486	614	742	86	214	230	367	495	623	751	95	223	239	356	484	612	740	84	212	228	10990		
10990	201	329	345	473	601	729	73	198	326	342	470	598	726	70	207	335	351	479	607	735	79	196	324	340	468	596	724	68	10990		
10990	713	57	185	313	441	457	585	710	54	182	310	438	454	582	719	63	191	319	447	463	591	708	52	180	308	436	452	580	10990		
10990	553	569	697	41	169	297	425	550	566	694	38	166	294	422	559	575	703	47	175	303	431	548	564	692	36	164	292	420	10990		
10990	281	409	537	665	681	25	153	278	406	534	662	678	22	150	287	415	543	671	687	31	159	276	404	532	660	676	20	148	10990		
	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	

We observe that it is not possible to have equal magic sums of order 7 as it is impossible to divide magic square sum of order 28 by 4, i.e., $10990/4 := 2747.5$. In this case, all the 16 blocks of order 7 are **pandiagonal** magic squares with different magic sums resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 given in example below.

Example 3.3. *A pandiagonal magic square of order 4, formed by 16 magic square sums of each 7×7 block is given by.*

		10990	10990	10990	10990
	2737	2772	2695	2786	10990
10990	2702	2779	2744	2765	10990
10990	2800	2709	2758	2723	10990
10990	2751	2730	2793	2716	10990
	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990

3.1.3 Third Approach: 4 Blocks of Order 14

Example 3.4. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 28 formed by 4 blocks of magic squares of order 14 constructed according to Example ?? is given by

																											10990	
1	377	761	448	552	312	232	128	65	633	584	712	497	193	2	378	762	447	551	311	231	127	66	634	583	711	498	194	10990
585	64	440	704	752	505	345	465	16	209	280	329	152	649	586	63	439	703	751	506	346	466	15	210	279	330	151	650	10990
504	648	121	545	688	249	320	24	185	104	385	393	593	736	503	647	122	546	687	250	319	23	186	103	386	394	594	735	10990
760	441	600	184	617	457	17	305	136	680	89	384	560	265	759	442	599	183	618	458	18	306	135	679	90	383	559	266	10990
656	336	217	48	481	344	113	401	529	248	689	97	744	592	655	335	218	47	482	343	114	402	530	247	690	98	743	591	10990
416	40	353	145	81	664	713	616	777	296	176	536	233	449	415	39	354	146	82	663	714	615	778	295	175	535	234	450	10990
73	137	528	225	9	609	784	657	720	368	488	201	288	408	74	138	527	226	10	610	783	658	719	367	487	202	287	407	10990
177	257	281	360	144	769	608	721	672	473	520	8	409	96	178	258	282	359	143	770	607	722	671	474	519	7	410	95	10990
120	169	240	289	376	728	665	776	601	425	25	472	88	521	119	170	239	290	375	727	666	775	602	426	26	471	87	522	10990
272	576	624	105	297	192	417	369	480	544	729	168	41	681	271	575	623	106	298	191	418	370	479	543	730	167	42	682	10990
321	745	697	456	273	72	537	208	337	56	424	569	640	160	322	746	698	455	274	71	538	207	338	55	423	570	639	159	10990
553	696	32	641	568	432	464	57	313	737	153	241	216	392	554	695	31	642	567	431	463	58	314	738	154	242	215	391	10990
705	513	489	768	224	129	80	256	400	561	328	632	361	49	706	514	490	767	223	130	79	255	399	562	327	631	362	50	10990
352	496	112	577	433	33	200	512	264	161	625	753	673	304	351	495	111	578	434	34	199	511	263	162	626	754	674	303	10990
3	379	763	446	550	310	230	126	67	635	582	710	499	195	4	380	764	445	549	309	229	125	68	636	581	709	500	196	10990
587	62	438	702	750	507	347	467	14	211	278	331	150	651	588	61	437	701	749	508	348	468	13	212	277	332	149	652	10990
502	646	123	547	686	251	318	22	187	102	387	395	595	734	501	645	124	548	685	252	317	21	188	101	388	396	596	733	10990
758	443	598	182	619	459	19	307	134	678	91	382	558	267	757	444	597	181	620	460	20	308	133	677	92	381	557	268	10990
654	334	219	46	483	342	115	403	531	246	691	99	742	590	653	333	220	45	484	341	116	404	532	245	692	100	741	589	10990
414	38	355	147	83	662	715	614	779	294	174	534	235	451	413	37	356	148	84	661	716	613	780	293	173	533	236	452	10990
75	139	526	227	11	611	782	659	718	366	486	203	286	406	76	140	525	228	12	612	781	660	717	365	485	204	285	405	10990
179	259	283	358	142	771	606	723	670	475	518	6	411	94	180	260	284	357	141	772	605	724	669	476	517	5	412	93	10990
118	171	238	291	374	726	667	774	603	427	27	470	86	523	117	172	237	292	373	725	668	773	604	428	28	469	85	524	10990
270	574	622	107	299	190	419	371	478	542	731	166	43	683	269	573	621	108	300	189	420	372	477	541	732	165	44	684	10990
323	747	699	454	275	70	539	206	339	54	422	571	638	158	324	748	700	453	276	69	540	205	340	53	421	572	637	157	10990
555	694	30	643	566	430	462	59	315	739	155	243	214	390	556	693	29	644	565	429	461	60	316	740	156	244	213	389	10990
707	515	491	766	222	131	78	254	398	563	326	630	363	51	708	516	492	765	221	132	77	253	397	564	325	629	364	52	10990
350	494	110	579	435	35	198	510	262	163	627	755	675	302	349	493	109	580	436	36	197	509	261	164	628	756	676	301	10990
10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990	10990

In this case, all the 4 blocks of order 14 are magic squares with equal magic sums $S_{14 \times 14} := 5495$. The middle blocks in all the magic squares of order 14 are **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums $S_{4 \times 4} := 2770$.

3.2 Magic Square of Order 30

In this subsection, we shall present four different ways of writing block-wise magic square of order 30. One as 5×6 , i.e., magic square formed by 36 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5. Second as 6×5 , i.e., magic square formed by 25 blocks of magic squares of order 6. The third as 10×3 , i.e., magic square formed by

sum of order 30 by 10, i.e., $13515/10 := 1351.5$. In this case, all the 100 blocks are magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums resulting in a magic square of order 10:

Example 3.6. *Magic sums of 100 blocks of magic squares of order 3 lead us to a magic square of order 10 is given by*

										13515
96	2598	1221	1725	429	2013	1482	2310	717	924	13515
2031	375	2589	1194	1527	978	2256	123	1752	690	13515
1185	1779	654	2337	951	420	2058	1446	2553	132	13515
1797	150	2022	933	636	2274	1239	2535	411	1518	13515
1473	906	1788	2040	1212	645	2571	447	114	2319	13515
2292	1203	366	708	2580	1491	177	1734	969	1995	13515
699	1464	987	141	2265	2562	1770	1248	1986	393	13515
960	672	2283	2526	168	1257	384	2049	1455	1761	13515
2544	2067	1500	402	1743	159	915	681	2328	1176	13515
438	2301	105	1509	2004	1716	663	942	1230	2607	13515
13515										

3.2.2 First Approach: 36 Blocks of Order 5

Example 3.7. *A magic square of order 30 formed by 36 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 5 constructed according to Example 1.3 is given by*

						13515
2165	2275	2300	2330	2245	2200	13515
2305	2195	2335	2230	2265	2185	13515
2220	2190	2225	2295	2315	2270	13515
2320	2240	2180	2280	2210	2285	13515
2255	2325	2215	2175	2310	2235	13515
2250	2290	2260	2205	2170	2340	13515
13515						

3.2.3 Second Approach: 25 Blocks of Order 6

Example 3.9. *A magic square of order 30 formed by 25 blocks of magic squares of order 6 constructed according to Example 1.4 is given by*

In this case, the magic square is **pandiagonal bimagic** with **magic** and **bimagic** sums, $S_{32 \times 32} := 16400$ and $Sb_{32 \times 32} := 11201200$ respectively. All the block of order 8 are magic squares with equal magic sums, $S_{8 \times 8} := 4100$. Moreover, each block of order 8 is either **bimagic** or **semi-bimagic** squares resulting in a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4:

Example 3.13. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 formed by 16 *bimagic* or *semi-bimagic* squares of order 8 is given by

		11201200	11201200	11201200	11201200
	2808468	2775684	2857700	2759348	11201200
11201200	2857652	2759396	2808452	2775700	11201200
11201200	2759300	2857620	2775732	2808548	11201200
11201200	2775780	2808500	2759316	2857604	11201200
	11201200	11201200	11201200	11201200	11201200

Sum of semi-diagonals also forms a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4.

3.4 Magic Squares of Order 33

In this subsection, we shall present two different ways of writing block-wise magic square of order 33. One as 11×3 , i.e., magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 11 with equal magic sums. Second as 3×11 , i.e., 121 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with equal magic sums.

3.4.1 First Approach: 121 Blocks of Order 3

Example 3.14. A *pandiagonal* magic square of order 33 formed by 121 blocks of *semi-magic* squares of order 3 constructed according to Example 1.1 is given by

3.6 Magic Squares of Order 36

In this subsection, we shall present six different ways of writing block-wise magic square of order 36. One as 4×9 , i.e., magic square formed by 81 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. Second as 12×3 , i.e., magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 12. Third, 9×4 , i.e., magic square formed by 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3. Forth as, 3×12 , i.e., magic square formed by 144 blocks of magic squares of order 3. Fifth as, 6×6 , i.e., magic square formed by 36 blocks of magic squares of order 6 with equal magic sums. Sixth as 4×9 , i.e., 16 blocks of bimagic squares of order 9. In the first four cases, the magic square of order 36 is **pandiagonal**, while in the fifth and sixth it is just a magic square of order 36.

3.6.1 First Approach: 144 Blocks of Order 3

It is impossible to have all the 3×3 blocks of equal sums as 23346 is not divisible by 12, i.e., $23346/12 := 1945.5$. Below is an example of a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 36 where each block of order 3 is a magic square with different magic sums giving total 144 blocks:

Example 3.18. *A **pandiagonal** magic square of order 36 formed by 144 blocks of magic squares of order 3 constructed according to Example 1.1 is given by*

		23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346
	1464	1158	1797	2481	2787	2148	438	780	123	3399	3057	3714	23346
23346	1806	1473	1140	2139	2472	2805	132	447	762	3705	3390	3075	23346
23346	1149	1788	1482	2796	2157	2463	771	114	456	3066	3723	3381	23346
23346	483	789	150	3354	3048	3687	1509	1167	1824	2436	2778	2121	23346
23346	141	474	807	3696	3363	3030	1815	1500	1185	2130	2445	2760	23346
23346	798	159	465	3039	3678	3372	1176	1833	1491	2769	2112	2454	23346
23346	3453	3111	3768	492	834	177	2427	2733	2094	1410	1104	1743	23346
23346	3759	3444	3129	186	501	816	2085	2418	2751	1752	1419	1086	23346
23346	3120	3777	3435	825	168	510	2742	2103	2409	1095	1734	1428	23346
23346	2382	2724	2067	1455	1113	1770	3408	3102	3741	537	843	204	23346
23346	2076	2391	2706	1761	1446	1131	3750	3417	3084	195	528	861	23346
23346	2715	2058	2400	1122	1779	1437	3093	3732	3426	852	213	519	23346
	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346

The above magic square of order 36 is also formed by 16 blocks of magic square of order 9 resulting in a pan magic square of order 4:

Example 3.20. *Magic sums of pandiagonal magic squares of order 9 of Exemple 3.18 lead us to a pandiagonal magic of order 4 given by*

		23346	23346	23346	23346
	4419	7416	1341	10170	23346
23346	1422	10089	4500	7335	23346
23346	10332	1503	7254	4257	23346
23346	7173	4338	10251	1584	23346
	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346

3.6.2 Second Approach: 81 Blocks of Order 4

Example 3.21. *A pandiagonal magic square of order 36 formed by 81 blocks of pandiagonal magic squares of order 4 constructed according to Example 1.2 is given by*

Example 3.24. *Magic sums of pandiagonal magic squares of order 9 lead us to a pandiagonal magic of order 4 given by*

		23346	23346	23346	23346
	5823	5868	5769	5886	23346
23346	5778	5877	5832	5859	23346
23346	5904	5787	5850	5805	23346
23346	5841	5814	5895	5796	23346
	23346	23346	23346	23346	23346

3.6.5 Fifth Approach: 9 Blocks of Order 12

Example 3.25. *A pandiagonal magic square of order 36 formed by 9 blocks of pandiagonal magic squares of order 12 constructed according to Example 1.12 is given by*

4 Author's Contributions to Magic Squares

The **item-wise** author's work on magic squares is as follows:

1. *Digital Numbers Magic Squares* - [13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 45];
2. *Connections with Genetic Tables and Shannon's entropy* - [20];
3. *Selfie and Palindromic-type Magic Squares* - [21, 36, 45];
4. *Intervally Distributed and Block-Wise Magic Squares* - [22, 23, 24, 36];
5. *Multi-digits and Number Patterns Magic Squares* - [25, 35];
6. *Perfect Square Sum Magic Squares with Uniformity, Minimum Sum and Pythagorean Triples* - [26, 27];
7. *Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares* - [19, 28, 29, 30, 31, 34, 37, 39];
8. *Magic Crosses: Repeated and Non Repeated Entries* - [32];
9. *Representations of Letters and Numbers With Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders 4 and 6* - [33];
10. *Bordered Magic Squares* - [40, 41, 42, 43, 44];
11. *2-Digits Magic and Bimagic Squares* - [45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52].

References

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<https://www.theguardian.com/science/2020/jan/27/can-you-solve-it-toot-toot-for-world-palindrome-day>, Jan. 27,
2020.
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